

1 Obstacle arrangement can control flows through 2 porous obstructions

3 Fei He¹, Hongwei An^{1,†}, Marco Ghisalberti^{1,2}, Scott Draper^{1,2},
4 Chengjiao Ren¹, Paul Branson³ and Liang Cheng^{1,4}

Q1

5 ¹School of Engineering, The University of Western Australia, 35 Stirling Highway, Crawley, WA 6009,
6 Australia

Q3

7 ²Oceans Graduate School, The University of Western Australia, 35 Stirling Highway, Crawley, WA 6009,
8 Australia

9 ³Oceans and Atmosphere, CSIRO, 35 Stirling Highway, Crawley, WA 6009, Australia

10 ⁴Guangzhou International Campus, South China University of Technology, Guangzhou, 511442, PR China

11 (Received 15 April 2023; revised 15 April 2024; accepted 16 May 2024)

12 Existing work suggests that the arrangement among elements of an obstruction may
13 influence the bulk velocity through it, but the physical mechanisms for the arrangement
14 influence are not yet clear. This has motivated the present study, in which direct numerical
15 simulation is used to investigate flow through a porous obstruction modelled by an array
16 of cylinders at a resolution sufficient to observe interactions between wakes of individual
17 elements. The arrangement is altered by varying gap ratio G/d (1.2–18, where G is distance
18 between two adjacent cylinders and d is cylinder diameter), array-to-element diameter ratio
19 D/d (3.6–200, where D is the array diameter) and incident flow angle θ (0° – 30°). Based
20 on the element arrangement, whilst the average root-mean-square lift and drag coefficients
21 can vary by an order of magnitude, the average drag coefficient of individual cylinders $\overline{C_d}$
22 and the bulk velocity are found to vary by up to 50% and a factor of 2, respectively. These
23 arrangement effects are a consequence of the variation in flow and drag characteristics of
24 individual cylinders within the array. The element-scale flow structure within an array is
25 therefore characterised across a range of arrangements. The downstream flow evolution
26 within the array shares similarities to that observed for a single line of cylinders. Across
27 the full range of arrangements modelled, it is confirmed that the bulk velocity is governed
28 by flow blockage parameter ($\Gamma'_D = \overline{C_d}aD/(1 - \phi)$, where a is frontal element area per
29 unit volume and ϕ is solid volume fraction). The arrangement effects become most critical
30 in the intermediate range of Γ'_D (0.5–1.5), due to the high variability in element-scale

Q4

† Email address for correspondence: hongwei.an@uwa.edu.au

31 flow characteristics. This paper proposes a framework for describing and predicting flow
 32 through a circular array of cylinders of different arrangements.

33 **Key words:** flow-structure interactions, porous media, wakes

34 1. Introduction

35 Practical porous obstructions in water flows can be arranged in various configurations.
 36 For instance, the transplanted mangrove shoots for restoration programmes are normally
 37 arranged into parallel inline rows (figure 1a); jacket structures are designed as a
 38 three-dimensional (3-D) truss with elements often having different orientation depending
 39 on the local load they withstand (figure 1b); foundation piles can be organised in a
 40 concentric ring (figure 1c); and tidal turbines are often arranged in staggered or inline
 41 patterns (figure 1d). The arrangement of these systems is often driven by hydrodynamic
 42 factors. For instance, arranging a number of turbines with the inline arrangement leads to
 43 lower power generation due to weaker wake interaction at the scale of individual turbines in
 44 comparison with the staggered configuration (Draper & Nishino 2014). Aquatic vegetation
 45 tends to self-organise into parallel rows of shoots normal to the flow direction which leads
 46 to reduction in hydrodynamic forces on individual shoots and velocity between adjacent
 47 rows; the force reduction makes the shoots less vulnerable to bending and the velocity
 48 reduction contributes to stabilising mobile bed loads within the vegetated region (Fonseca,
 49 Koehl & Kopp 2007). These applications highlight the importance of investigating the
 50 hydrodynamic influences of arrangement.

Q5
Q6

51 Although their geometries vary widely, arrangement effects in these porous systems can
 52 be investigated by examining the simpler problem of an arrangement of vertical circular
 53 cylinders with maintaining interaction between individual cylinders as the key element
 54 in this problem (see figure 2). When the total number of cylinders is small ($N \lesssim 9$) or
 55 cylinders align in a single line, the arrangement effect on flow patterns and aerodynamic
 56 forces of individual cylinders (element scale) has been the focus of extensive studies. In the
 57 simplest, classical two-cylinder system, ‘inline’ (figure 2a) and ‘side-by-side’ (figure 2b)
 58 configurations form when the line joining the cylinder centres is aligned with ($\theta = 0^\circ$)
 59 and perpendicular to ($\theta = 90^\circ$) the incident flow, respectively (Zdravkovich 1977); a
 60 ‘staggered’ pattern is formed when $0^\circ < \theta < 90^\circ$ (figure 2c). Following this, three cylinders
 61 with equilateral configuration (figure 2d) (Bao, Zhou & Huang 2010; Chen *et al.* 2020)
 62 and four, six and nine cylinders with inline pattern at different θ (figure 2e) (Lam, Li & So
 63 2003; Wang *et al.* 2013; Gao *et al.* 2020; Yin *et al.* 2020) have been studied. More recently,
 64 a single line of cylinders (figure 2f) has been investigated in an attempt to understand the
 65 flow evolution process along a line of a large number of cylinders (Hosseini, Griffith &
 66 Leontini 2020; Zhu, Zhong & Zhou 2021; Eizadi *et al.* 2022).

67 The hydrodynamics of a small cluster of cylinders (figure 2a–e) and a single line of
 68 cylinders (figure 2f) has been shown to be primarily governed by the gap ratio G/d (G is
 69 the centre-to-centre distance between two nearest cylinders and d is the cylinder diameter;
 70 see figure 2a), the orientation angle θ (figure 2c) and the Reynolds number $Re_d = U_\infty d/\nu$
 71 (in which ν is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid and U_∞ is the upstream velocity of the
 72 array) (Lam *et al.* 2003; Sumner 2010; Chen *et al.* 2020; Yin *et al.* 2020). Through varying
 73 G/d , θ and Re_d , flow regimes have been mapped out based on a variety of element-scale
 74 flow patterns and force coefficients (Sumner 2010; Zhou & Alam 2016; Chen *et al.* 2020;
 75 Gao *et al.* 2020). A general conclusion from these studies is that as G/d decreases, the

Obstacle arrangement can control flows

Figure 1. Arrangements of real systems. (a) Parallel rows of transplanted mangrove shoots for restoration programmes; (b) jacket structures arranged as a 3-D truss; (c) foundation piles arranged in a concentric ring; (d) inline tidal turbines.

Figure 2. A summary of cylinder arrangements used in existing literature. (a–c) Two cylinders with different arrangements; (d) three equilateral-triangular cylinders with arbitrary flow angle; (e) 4–9 cylinders arranged in rectangular configuration; (f) a single line of cylinders. ‘C1’ represents the first cylinder in the line; (g) A circular array of cylinders arranged in multiple lines. Here U_∞ is the velocity of the incident flow, d is the cylinder diameter, G is the centre-to-centre distance between two nearest cylinders, θ is the orientation angle of incident flow relative to the primary axis of the array, D is the array diameter and α is the intrinsic angle defined based on three nearest cylinders. The array-to-element scale ratio D/d is important in influencing flow through a circular array in (g), which is not considered in the earlier studies with configurations in (a–f).

76 element-scale vortex structures become less dominant, and all the cylinders collectively
 77 behave effectively as a single body to form large-scale vortex shedding. The threshold of
 78 G/d for the transition from the element-scale-dominant to ‘single-body’-dominant flow
 79 pattern depends on θ and Re_d .

80 In comparison with these two scenarios, a large number ($N \gtrsim 9$) of cylinders are
 81 normally considered in the form of a circular array (see figure 2g), which has received
 82 comparatively little attention. The circular array has the advantage of eliminating the
 83 influence of array shape on flow and drag characteristics when varying θ (Chang &
 84 Constantinescu 2015). A key distinction from the other two scenarios reviewed above
 85 is that the array dimension (D) and the solid volume fraction ($\phi = (\pi/4)nd^2$, where

86 n is the number of cylinders per unit area) have been used to parameterise the finite
 87 array of cylinders (e.g. Nicolle & Eames 2011; Zong & Nepf 2012). Following this,
 88 the array-to-element diameter ratio (D/d) was identified as an important parameter in
 89 controlling the array-induced flow structures (Chang & Constantinescu 2015). For a
 90 circular array, previous studies were mainly focused on flow structures behind the array
 91 (array scale) (e.g. Zong & Nepf 2012), velocity of bulk flow through it (bleeding flow)
 92 (e.g. Chen *et al.* 2012) and total drag on the array (e.g. Cheng *et al.* 2019) when varying
 93 the array arrangement. It has been shown that a denser array (lower ϕ) coincides with
 94 lower averaged drag coefficient of individual cylinders $\overline{C_d}$ (Chang & Constantinescu 2015;
 95 Cheng *et al.* 2019), and lower bleeding velocity and hence more unstable array-scale wake
 96 behind the array (Ball *et al.* 1996; Zong & Nepf 2012). Additionally, as shown by the
 97 data in Zhao *et al.* (2015) (for square arrays), the $\overline{C_d}$ value can be even decreased by
 98 36 %, and the von Kármán vortex street was suppressed in the array wake by changing the
 99 array from a staggered to an inline arrangement (changing θ and α simultaneously). These
 100 results highlight the significant effects of cylinder arrangements on the array-scale flow
 101 and drag characteristics for an array of a large number of cylinders. However, there is no
 102 quantitative guidance to determine if arrangement effects are critical for a given porous
 103 array. More importantly, the physical mechanism for these arrangement effects has yet to
 104 be investigated.

105 A possible mechanism is associated with the element-scale flow characteristics within
 106 an array. This idea is informed by the similarities of flow structures between a single
 107 line of cylinders (Hosseini *et al.* 2020; Zhu *et al.* 2021; Eizadi *et al.* 2022) and an
 108 array of multiple lines of cylinders (Ziada 2006; Zhao *et al.* 2015). Research on a
 109 small number of and a single line of cylinders has revealed that the drag on individual
 110 cylinders depends on the local flow characteristics around these cylinders. For instance, the
 111 formation of characteristic flow structures such as two-row structure (TRS) and shear-layer
 112 reattachment (SLR) can cause significant drag reduction to the elements subjected to these
 113 flow structures (e.g. Sumner 2010; Hosseini *et al.* 2020). It is suspected that the correlation
 114 between local drag and flow characteristics should also exist in a multiple-line array. It is
 115 therefore hypothesised that varying the cylinder arrangement (both array geometry and
 116 array orientation relative to the incident flow) will result in variations in the local flow and
 117 drag characteristics of individual elements. Consequently, this may result in changes in the
 118 overall drag force on the array, the bulk flow through the array and hence the array-scale
 119 wake characteristics. One of motivations of the present study is to examine this hypothesis
 120 based on the well-established knowledge of the flows past a small number of cylinders
 121 ($N \lesssim 9$) and a single line of cylinders. This contributes to linking flow through the large
 122 circular array of cylinders with flow past the small number and the single line of cylinders.

123 To account for the array-scale effects, previous studies have defined the array-induced
 124 flow modifications through the dimensionless flow blockage parameter (Rominger & Nepf
 125 2011; Chang & Constantinescu 2015). This parameter is derived from the two-dimensional
 126 (2-D) streamwise momentum equation that applies to the region of the array:

$$127 \quad \underbrace{\bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial x}}_i + \bar{v} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x} - \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \frac{\overline{C_d} a D}{(1-\phi)} \bar{u} (\bar{u}^2 + \bar{v}^2)^{1/2}}_{ii}, \quad (1.1)$$

128 where u and v are respectively the velocity components in the streamwise (x) and
 129 transverse (y) directions for which an overbar represents the time-average operation, p
 130 is the pressure, ρ is the fluid density and $a = nd$ is the frontal area of cylinders per unit
 131 area within the array. Note that the Reynolds stress term is omitted from this equation

132 since this term is negligible compared with the drag term (ii) within the array (Rominger
 133 & Nepf 2011). The bulk bleeding flow is determined by the ratio of term ‘ii’ in (1.1) of
 134 drag on the array elements retarding the flow and the advection term ‘i’ describing the flow
 135 deceleration through the array (Chang & Constantinescu 2015). Using the characteristic
 136 values

$$137 \quad x \sim D, \quad u \sim U_\infty \quad (1.2a,b)$$

138 to scale the ratio of these two terms yields the important non-dimensional flow blockage
 139 parameter:

$$140 \quad \Gamma'_D = \frac{\overline{C_d} a D}{(1 - \phi)}. \quad (1.3)$$

141 When using flow blockage parameter to describe the flow, it has relied upon significant
 142 assumptions about $\overline{C_d}$ in the absence of direct measurement of $\overline{C_d}$. For instance, the
 143 averaged drag coefficient was often taken to be unity (Zong & Nepf 2012), in which case
 144 the flow blockage parameter is termed as Γ_D . The geometric flow blockage Γ_D differs
 145 from the effective flow blockage parameter Γ'_D where $\overline{C_d}$ is from direct measurement.
 146 Parameter Γ_D captures the variation of bleeding velocity due to the changes in the
 147 solid volume fraction ϕ (a parameter characterising the array configuration in a spatially
 148 averaged sense) but not for the changes in the local element arrangement (local positioning
 149 between individual elements relative to the incident flow, e.g. staggered and inline) (Chen
 150 *et al.* 2012; Nair *et al.* 2023). For instance, at the same Γ_D (and ϕ), the bleeding velocity
 151 can be decreased by approximately 20% when the array changes from the inline to
 152 staggered arrangement, as seen in the data from Takemura & Tanaka (2007). One possible
 153 interpretation to the incompleteness of Γ_D is that the cylinder arrangement significantly
 154 influences $\overline{C_d}$ as shown in existing work (e.g. Takemura & Tanaka 2007; Zhao *et al.* 2015),
 155 which is, however, not properly accounted for in any part of Γ_D . Over a wide range
 156 of Γ_D , it is not clear how $\overline{C_d}$ varies due to changes in arrangement, which could lead
 157 to high discrepancy from unity. Therefore, another motivation of the present work is to
 158 systematically explore the variability of $\overline{C_d}$ with the cylinder arrangement to confirm the
 159 explanation of incompleteness of Γ_D .

160 The goal of this paper is to investigate flow through a circular array with
 161 $D/d \sim O(10-100)$ through 3-D direct numerical simulations (DNS) with complementary
 162 2-D numerical simulations, with three major objectives: (i) to interpret, at the element
 163 scale, the physical mechanism for cylinder arrangement effects; (ii) to identify the
 164 parameter range where arrangement effects are critical; and (iii) to develop a universal
 165 framework for describing flow through a finite circular array of any arrangement.

166 2. Methodology

167 2.1. Numerical approach

168 Three-dimensional DNS of the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations were utilised for
 169 solving the continuity and momentum equations:

$$170 \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \quad (2.1)$$

$$171 \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}, \quad (2.2)$$

172 where $\mathbf{u} = (u, v, w)(x, y, z, t)$ is the velocity field and t is the time. Equations (2.1) and (2.2)
 173 were solved by using a spectral/hp element method embedded in the open-source software

174 package Nektar++ (Cantwell *et al.* 2015). A second-order time integration method was
 175 applied, together with a velocity correction scheme in the Galerkin formula, which are
 176 detailed in existing work (e.g. Guermond & Shen 2003; Blackburn & Sherwin 2004; Vos
 177 *et al.* 2011).

178 A quasi-3-D approach is employed in Nektar++ as detailed in Cantwell *et al.* (2015).
 179 Specifically, the spectral/*hp* element method was employed in the (x, y) plane and a Fourier
 180 expansion was used in the spanwise direction (z direction) to resolve 3-D structures. Only a
 181 2-D mesh was therefore required for this quasi-3-D approach. The solution of the velocity
 182 and pressure fields can be expressed through $N_z/2$ Fourier modes in the spanwise direction,
 183 where N_z is the total quadrature points (Fourier planes) of the z -direction expansion basis.

184 The mesh resolution in the spectral/*hp* element method is determined by both the
 185 distribution of the h -type elements and the interpolation order N_p for the p -type refinement,
 186 such that the number of cells in the x - y plane equals $N_m \times (N_p - 1)^2$, where N_m represents
 187 the total number of macro-elements in the h -type mesh. In this study, fifth-order Lagrange
 188 polynomials were used on Gauss–Lobatto–Legendre quadrature points ($N_p = 5$). The
 189 number of macro-elements used to discretise the cylinder surface $N_c = 48$, and a radial
 190 thickness of the first macro-element next to each cylinder surface $\Delta/d \approx 0.03$. These
 191 parameters are determined based on other spectral element studies for flow past multiple
 192 cylinders at comparable Re_d ranges (e.g. Ren *et al.* 2019; 2021a,b). The expansion ratios
 193 of mesh are kept below 1.2 within the domain. The number of cells in the x - y plane varies
 194 from 210 000 to 3 375 000 as N increases from 7 to 109.

195 For the selections of spanwise length L_z and resolution N_z for 3-D simulations, different
 196 strategies are performed owing to the distinct wake characteristics of the array.

- 197 (i) When the elements are sparsely distributed within the array ($G/d \gtrsim 3$), existing
 198 research implies that the three-dimensionality develops directly in the wakes of
 199 individual elements. Hence, the spanwise length of $1D$ with a resolution of $\sim 0.2d$
 200 is employed to ensure adequate resolution of element-scale 3-D flow structures (see
 201 table 1). Such length and resolution were found to be adequate to resolve the 3-D
 202 flow structures for an isolated solid cylinder (e.g. Jiang & Cheng 2021) and two
 203 side-by-side cylinders (Ren *et al.* 2023).
- 204 (ii) When the elements are closely packed ($G/d \lesssim 3$), the element-scale vortex shedding
 205 is expected to be suppressed due to limited gaps between individual cylinders,
 206 whereas the array-scale vortex shedding develops behind the array. To examine the
 207 three-dimensionality in the array-scale wake behind the array, the spanwise length
 208 is doubled to $2D$ with a spanwise resolution of $\sim 0.2d$.

209 When doubling the spanwise length or the Fourier plane number for the sparsest array 2^*
 210 and the densest array 16^* in table 1, a relatively small statistical difference in the average
 211 drag coefficient and bleeding velocity (e.g. relative differences in $\overline{C_d}$ are within 3 %) was
 212 observed. This suggests that the spanwise lengths and resolutions used here were sufficient
 213 to resolve the full 3-D flow structures. Spanwise lengths and resolutions of (i, ii) have also
 214 been shown being adequate to resolve the 3-D flow structures of a porous array in Chang
 215 & Constantinescu (2015).

216 A circular computational domain was used, with detailed mesh configurations shown
 217 in figure 3. A porous array of diameter D was placed at the centre of the domain, i.e. ($x,$
 218 y) = (0, 0). The radius of the domain is $r = 20D$, with the wall blockage ratio $D/2r = 0.025$.
 219 Such a blockage ratio has negligible effects on the hydrodynamic forces on the array
 220 (Nicolle & Eames 2011).

	Case	N	G/d	θ	Γ_D	Re_D	$\frac{L_z}{D}$	$\frac{L_z}{d}$	N_z	$\frac{\Delta_z}{d}$	N_{ele} (million)	Computational cost (core hour, million)
3-D	1*	31	14.7	0°	0.50	15 800	1	79	395	0.20	113.63	2.765
	2*	31	14.7	30°	0.50	15 800	1	79	395	0.20	113.63	2.534
	3*	31	8	0°	0.93	8660	1	43.3	224	0.19	217.88	4.625
	4*	31	6	0°	1.24	6540	1	32.7	160	0.20	78.274	0.595
	5*	31	6	30°	1.24	6540	1	32.7	160	0.20	78.274	0.595
	6*	31	4.5	0°	1.68	4960	1	24.8	128	0.19	59.926	0.499
	7*	31	4.5	10°	1.68	4960	1	24.8	128	0.19	59.926	0.499
	8*	31	4.5	30°	1.68	4960	1	24.8	128	0.19	58.049	0.461
	9*	31	3.8	0°	2.01	4220	1	21.1	96	0.22	44.622	0.553
	10*	31	2.7	0°	2.98	3060	2	30.6	160	0.19	67.110	0.461
	11*	31	2.7	10°	2.98	3060	2	30.6	160	0.19	67.110	0.461
	12*	31	2.7	30°	2.98	3060	2	30.6	160	0.19	64.709	0.645
	13*	31	2.3	30°	4.83	2200	2	22	96	0.23	29.491	0.307
	14*	31	1.9	30°	4.83	2200	2	22	96	0.23	29.491	0.307
	15*	31	1.2	0°	12.93	1460	2	14.6	64	0.22	31.363	0.346
	16*	31	1.2	30°	12.93	1460	2	14.6	64	0.22	31.363	0.346
	17*	109	8	0°	1.65	17 132	1	85.6	390	0.22	408.413	6.144
	18*	109	4.5	0°	2.99	9720	1	48.6	256	0.19	158.471	3.686
	19*	109	4.5	30°	2.99	9720	1	48.6	256	0.19	182.795	3.789
	20*	109	2.5	0°	5.91	5500	2	55	256	0.21	133.788	2.048
2-D	1	7	17	0°	0.26	7000	—	—	—	—	0.237	0.004
	10	7	1.7	0°	3.17	880	—	—	—	—	0.215	0.003
	22	31	14.7	0°	0.50	15 800	—	—	—	—	0.926	0.013
	48	31	1.2	30°	12.93	1460	—	—	—	—	0.871	0.026
	59	109	17	0°	0.77	36 180	—	—	—	—	3.376	0.039
	75	109	1.2	0°	24.2	2740	—	—	—	—	2.691	0.060

Table 1. Summary of mesh and simulation statistics at $Re_d = 200$ for 3-D cases and 2-D cases. Parameters L_z , N_z , Δ_z and N_{ele} represent the spanwise length of the array, the number of Fourier planes, the spanwise resolution and the total number of mesh cells in the domain, respectively.

221 A Dirichlet velocity boundary condition ($u = U_\infty$ and $v = 0$) was specified on the
 222 inlet (front half of the circumference of the computational domain), while on the outlet
 223 boundary (back half of the circumference) a Neumann velocity boundary condition
 224 ($\partial u / \partial n = 0$ and $\partial v / \partial n = 0$, where n is the normal vector to the outlet boundary) was
 225 applied. A no-slip boundary condition was enforced on all cylinder walls. As suggested
 226 by Blackburn & Sherwin (2004) and Karniadakis, Israeli & Orszag (1991), a high-order
 227 Neumann pressure condition was specified across domain boundaries, with the exception
 228 of a reference zero Dirichlet pressure condition employed on the outlet boundary. The
 229 time-step size was chosen based on a Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy limit of 0.5.

230 The present computations were performed on a Cray XC40 system supercomputer. For
 231 each case, parallel simulation was conducted on multiple computing nodes with scalability
 232 checks. The computational costs of 3-D simulations with $10\,000t^*$ are summarised in
 233 table 1. The cost for 3-D simulation surged extraordinarily due to the extremely large
 234 number of mesh cells in the domain. For instance, for the array 16* with 109 cylinders, the
 235 total number of mesh cells is approximately 0.18 billion; the parallel computation for this
 236 case was done with 5120 cores, with 3.8 million core hours for $10\,000t^*$ (see table 1). The
 237 total computational cost of wall-clock time for these 3-D simulations is 31.7 million core
 238 hours.

Figure 3. An example of mesh topology for an array of cylinders with $N = 31$. (a) Global view of entire computational domain; (b) close-up view of h -type mesh distribution for the cylinder array; (c) close-up view of detailed h -type mesh distribution around seven cylinders around the array centre; (d) close-up view of a hp -refined mesh around the central cylinder consisting of fifth-order Lagrange polynomials on Gauss–Lobatto–Legendre quadrature points, where p -type refined mesh is in grey. The overall mesh resolution is defined by both the distribution of the h -type meshes and the interpolation order N_p ($= 5$) for the p -type refinement.

239 Due to the high computational costs for 3-D simulations, 2-D simulations were
 240 conducted to increase the resolution of parameter space, serving as complement to the
 241 3-D simulations to conduct a parametric study across a wide highly resolved parameter
 242 space. The 2-D DNS has been used for examining arrangement effects on the array-scale
 243 wake at $(Re_d, Re_D) = (100, 2100)$ in Nicolle & Eames (2011) and on the drag and wake
 244 characteristics at $(500, 2500)$ in Nair *et al.* (2023) ($Re_D = U_\infty D/\nu$). More importantly,
 245 it was shown in figure 18(c) of Chang, Constantinescu & Tsai (2017) that there is good
 246 agreement on the average drag coefficient $\overline{C_d}$ among 2-D simulations with $(Re_d, Re_D) =$
 247 $(100, 2100)$ in Nicolle & Eames (2011), 3-D simulations with $(480, 10\,000)$ in Chang
 248 & Constantinescu (2015) and 3-D simulations with $(2010, 67\,000)$ and $(2010, 37\,500)$
 249 in Chang *et al.* (2017). These support the applicability of 2-D DNS in exploring the

250 arrangement effects. Besides the above justification based on the literature, independent
 251 evaluation about the applicability of 2-D simulations was made as a part of the parameter
 252 studies through comparing 2-D and 3-D flow and force characteristics. For a 2-D case, the
 253 computational cost ranged from approximately 3000 core hours for the smallest array with
 254 $N = 7$ cylinders to 60 000 core hours for the largest array with $N = 109$ (see table 1).

255 Each 2-D flow was simulated for at least 2000 non-dimensional time units (defined as
 256 $t^* = tU_\infty/d$) to reach a fully developed state. The 2-D simulation was then continued
 257 for at least $5000t^*$ (called full length) for statistical analysis. As the three-dimensionality
 258 in the system is weak, it took a longer time to reach a fully developed 3-D state, in
 259 comparison with the 2-D flow. Each 3-D flow was simulated at least $5000t^*$ to reach a
 260 fully developed stage, after which the 3-D simulation was run for at least another $5000t^*$
 261 for statistical analysis. The good agreement between the results (average drag coefficient,
 262 bleeding velocity) calculated with the full length of data and the second half of data for
 263 both the 2-D and 3-D cases (e.g. relative differences in $\overline{C_d}$ are within 0.1 %) suggests that
 264 the sampled length of data is statistically converged.

265 Following Chang & Constantinescu (2015), the numerical validation in the present study
 266 was conducted based on the simulations of flow past an isolated cylinder. The simulations
 267 were run at two limiting conditions: (1) the cylinders within the array are spaced far enough
 268 to have no wake effect ($\phi \approx 0$) and (2) the array becomes very dense to be a solid body
 269 ($\phi \approx 1$). Whilst the case for $\phi \approx 0$ was run at $Re_d = 200$ for both 2-D and 3-D simulations,
 270 the case for $\phi \approx 1$ was run at $Re_D = 1500$ where the diameter of the isolated cylinder is
 271 equal to the array diameter. This Reynolds number of 1500 (available in existing work) is
 272 close to the array Reynolds number (1469) for the densest array in the present study which
 273 is expected to manifest strongest three-dimensionality in the flow. Detailed numerical
 274 validations are shown in Appendices A1 and A2.

275 2.2. Quantification of flow and force characteristics

276 Drag forces, vorticity field and flow through the array (bleeding flow) are employed for
 277 quantifying the influence of arrangement on hydrodynamics of a porous array. Definitions
 278 of these variables are given in this section.

279 2.2.1. Force quantification

280 The force acting on the i th cylinder is characterised by drag and lift coefficients, which are
 281 defined as follows:

$$282 \quad C_{d,i} = \frac{F_{d,i}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho dU_\infty^2}, \quad C_{l,i} = \frac{F_{l,i}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho dU_\infty^2}, \quad (2.3a,b)$$

283 where $F_{d,i}$ and $F_{l,i}$ are the drag and lift forces on the i th cylinder (per unit length),
 284 respectively. The time-mean drag and lift coefficients are denoted as $\overline{C_{d,i}}$ and $\overline{C_{l,i}}$,
 285 respectively. The averaged drag force exerting on cylinders within the array is characterised
 286 by the average drag coefficient, which can be written as

$$287 \quad \overline{C_d} = \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N \overline{C_{d,i}}\right)}{N}. \quad (2.4)$$

Figure 4. The cylinder configuration for different number of cylinders ($N = 7, 19, 31, 55, 109$). The dot-dashed lines represent the circumferences of arrays.

288 The averaged fluctuating components of drag and lift coefficients can be quantified by
 289 the average root-mean-square drag and lift coefficients as

$$290 \quad \overline{C_{d,rms}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M (C_{d,i}^j - \overline{C_{d,i}})^2}, \quad \overline{C_{l,rms}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M (C_{l,i}^j - \overline{C_{l,i}})^2},$$

291 (2.5a,b)

292 where M is the number of discrete values in the time histories of $C_{d,i}$ and $C_{l,i}$.

293 2.2.2. Flow quantification

294 The vortex structures formed in the system can be identified through visualising the
 295 dimensionless vorticity field in the spanwise direction and streamwise direction, ω_z, ω_x
 296 which is defined as

$$297 \quad \omega_z = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}, \quad \omega_x = \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v}{\partial z}. \quad (2.6a,b)$$

298 The bulk bleeding flow through a porous array is characterised by a spatial-averaged
 299 time-mean streamwise velocity \bar{u}_p over the arc segments of $\mathbf{U} \cdot \mathbf{n} > 0$ (\mathbf{U} is the vector
 300 of mean velocity and \mathbf{n} is the normal vector of the circumference) around the array
 301 circumference (dashed circle in figure 4):

$$302 \quad \bar{u}_p = \frac{1}{P} \oint \bar{u} dp, \quad (2.7)$$

303 where P is summation of integrating arc segments for $\mathbf{U} \cdot \mathbf{n} > 0$. Note that the integrating
 304 arc segments for calculating \bar{u}_p are case-dependent and only part of the array perimeter. In
 305 3-D simulations, \bar{u} is post-processed on a spanwise-average flow field.

2.3. Dimensional analysis

306
307 In 3-D simulations, the time-mean drag $F_{d,i}$ and lift $F_{l,i}$ forces on each cylinder are related
308 to both the flow and array characteristics, which can be described by a function of nine
309 dimensional variables as

$$310 \quad F_{d,i} = \frac{1}{2} \overline{C_{d,i}} \rho d U_{\infty}^2 = f(G, d, D, \alpha, \theta, \rho, \mu, U_{\infty}), \quad (2.8)$$

$$311 \quad F_{l,i} = \frac{1}{2} \overline{C_{l,i}} \rho d U_{\infty}^2 = f(G, d, D, \alpha, \theta, \rho, \mu, U_{\infty}), \quad (2.9)$$

312 where μ is the dynamic viscosity. The Buckingham π theorem suggests the drag and lift
313 coefficients in this system are governed by five non-dimensional parameters as

$$314 \quad \overline{C_{d,i}} = f(G/d, D/d, \theta, \alpha, Re_d), \quad (2.10)$$

$$315 \quad \overline{C_{l,i}} = f(G/d, D/d, \theta, \alpha, Re_d). \quad (2.11)$$

316 Following (2.10), the average of drag coefficients of all cylinders within an array can be
317 expressed by

$$318 \quad \overline{C_d} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \overline{C_{d,i}} = f(G/d, D/d, \theta, \alpha, Re_d). \quad (2.12)$$

319 From the momentum balance, the bleeding velocity \bar{u}_p through a cylinder array with
320 regular arrangement is controlled by the flow blockage parameter, which can be expressed
321 by these independent dimensionless parameters (He 2023) as

$$322 \quad \frac{\bar{u}_p}{U_{\infty}} = f(\Gamma'_D) = f\left(\frac{\overline{C_d} a D}{(1-\phi)}\right) = f\left(\frac{2\overline{C_d}(D/d)}{(G/d)^2 \tan \alpha - \pi/4}\right). \quad (2.13)$$

323 It appears that changes to independent arrangement parameters in (2.13) not only
324 mathematically alter Γ'_D on the part of $aD/(1-\phi)$, but also vary it through the
325 hydrodynamic response of $\overline{C_d}$ as described in (2.12). The latter is, however, missed in
326 representative flow blockage parameter Γ_D in previous studies (e.g. Zong & Nepf 2012).

327 Similar relationships of lift and drag coefficients with arrangement as described in
328 (2.8)–(2.12) are expected in 2-D simulations. However, there would be an additional
329 parameter Ω on the right-hand side of these equations in 2-D simulations representing
330 the influence of three-dimensionality with removing the complexity of spanwise flow
331 variation. The three-dimensionality influence Ω is quantified through the root mean square
332 error, which is defined as

$$333 \quad \text{RMSE}_{\Omega} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{k=1}^M (\Pi_{k,2-D} - \Pi_{k,3-D})^2}{M}}, \quad (2.14)$$

334 where $\Pi_{k,2-D}$ and $\Pi_{k,3-D}$ are the corresponding variables (e.g. $\overline{C_d}$) in 2-D and 3-D
335 simulations, respectively. In the comparison of global quantities (e.g. $\overline{C_d}$, \bar{u}_p , \bar{u}), M is
336 the total number of data points from either 2-D or 3-D simulations conducted in both the
337 present and previous studies; in the comparison of local quantities for individual cylinders
338 (e.g. $\overline{C_{d,i}}$), M is the total number of cylinders within the array for a particular case.

339 Using 3-D simulations with complement 2-D simulations, arrangement effects are
340 systematically investigated by varying the values of G/d (in the range 1.2–18), D/d
341 (3.6–200) and θ (0° – 30°). For a given G/d , varying D/d is achieved by changing the total

342 number of cylinders N . The geometries for arrays with different N are shown in figure 4.
 343 In total, 320 cases (twenty 3-D cases) are simulated to investigate the arrangements, with
 344 testing conditions detailed in table 3 of Appendix B. The Reynolds number of individual
 345 elements is fixed at $Re_d = 200$. A constant intrinsic angle $\alpha = 60^\circ$ is used, which is
 346 representative of a porous obstruction with isotropic configuration. Note that, for an array
 347 with $\alpha = 60^\circ$, the flow field repeats after every θ interval of 30° such that our numerical
 348 results in the range $\theta = 0^\circ - 30^\circ$ can be extended to flows with $\theta = 30^\circ - 360^\circ$.

349 3. Results

350 3.1. Overview of flow through an array of cylinders

351 In this section, an overview of 3-D flow through an array of cylinders is presented based
 352 on four wake regimes (He *et al.* (2022, 2024), and presented in figure 5). In presenting
 353 this, comparison with results from 2-D simulations is made, which provides insights into
 354 the applicability of 2-D DNS in modelling flow through an array of cylinders.

355 These four wake regimes are: (i) the coupled individual wake (CI), in which the
 356 array shear layers are stabilised, and the array wake behind the array is dominated by
 357 the element-scale wakes of individual cylinders (figure 5*a,e*); (ii) the Kelvin-Helmholtz
 358 instability wake (KH), where the array shear layers are susceptible to Kelvin-Helmholtz
 359 instability to form two rows of KH vortices (figure 5*b,f*); (iii) the ‘steady + shedding’
 360 wake (SS), in which the two array shear layers remain independent in the steady region,
 361 before interacting to result in a von Kármán vortex street downstream (figure 5*c,g*); and (iv)
 362 the vortex street wake (VS), where a von Kármán vortex street forms immediately behind
 363 the array (figure 5*d,h*). As the flow transits from regime CI through to VS, the formation of
 364 element-scale vortices in wakes of individual cylinders is progressively suppressed within
 365 the array, coinciding with the increasingly dominant array-scale vortices developed behind
 366 the array.

367 Figure 5 shows that the flow exhibits 3-D features and 3-D flow structures can arise
 368 from either individual cylinders or the array depending on the regime. For instance, in
 369 regime CI (see figure 5*a,e*), it is seen that streamwise vortices develop in the wakes of
 370 cylinders at either side of the array. These vortices will merge and be dissipated rapidly in
 371 the near wake of the array as being convected downstream. As flow transits into regime
 372 KH (see figure 5*b,f*), whilst there is no 3-D flow structure forming within the array, the
 373 array-scale streamwise vortices form when the two rows of KH vortices, associated with
 374 each array shear layer, interact with each other to form a vortex street further downstream.
 375 In comparison to regimes CI and KH, the flow in regime SS exhibits a relatively weaker
 376 3-D feature (figure 5*c,g*), occurring where the two array shear layers interact to form vortex
 377 shedding. Finally, in regime VS, the porous array behaves similarly to an isolated solid
 378 cylinder in terms of formation of a 3-D von Kármán vortex street immediately behind the
 379 array (figure 5*d,h*).

380 The distribution of three-dimensionality in the system can be further illustrated by
 381 examining the time-mean spanwise kinetic energy, which is defined as

$$382 \quad E_z = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \frac{1}{2} w^2 / U_\infty^2 dt, \quad (3.1)$$

383 where T is the sample duration of fully developed flow and w^2 / U_∞^2 is post-processed
 384 on a spanwise-average flow field. This quantity has been used previously to check the
 385 three-dimensionality in the cylinder wake (e.g. Tong *et al.* 2014; Jiang *et al.* 2016).

Obstacle arrangement can control flows

Figure 5. For caption see next page.

Figure 5 (cntd). Flow characteristics for four regimes of the array-scale wake. (a–d) Cross-sectional instantaneous flow field (at $z/D=0$) from 3-D DNS, visualised by spanwise vorticity $\omega_x d/U_\infty = [-0.4, 0.4]$ for (a) coupled individual wake (CI), (b) Kelvin–Helmholtz instability wake (KH), (c) steady shedding wake (SS) and (d) vortex street wake (VS); isosurfaces of $\omega_x d/U_\infty = \pm 0.5$ (coloured by ω_x) for (e) CI, (f) KH, (g) SS and (h) VS. The four cases in regimes CI, KH, SS and VS have $G/d = 8, 4.5, 2.5, 1.2$ and $N = 31, 109, 31, 31$, respectively. As the flow transits from regime CI through to VS, the vortex structures behind the array progressively evolve from the element scale to the array scale, and the flow exhibits 3-D features largely behind the array rather than within the array.

386 Whilst in regime CI non-zero E_z values are distributed behind the array and around a
 387 few cylinders in the rear of the array (figure 6a), in regimes KH, SS and VS non-zero E_z
 388 values are only observed behind the array (figure 6b–d). Clearly, the flow exhibits 3-D
 389 features largely behind rather than within the array. This is consistent with figure 5 where
 390 the three-dimensionality is visualised by isosurfaces of streamwise vorticity.

391 Although 3-D structures form within the array in regime CI (figures 6a and 5a), the
 392 wake three-dimensionality of the element-scale wakes is relatively weak at $Re_d = 200$
 393 (Jiang *et al.* 2016), a Reynolds number close to the onset Reynolds number of 194 for
 394 an isolated cylinder (Williamson 1996). At $Re_d = 200$, the maximum difference in the
 395 average drag coefficient $\overline{C_d}$ for the two tandem cylinders across the range of $G/d = 1.5–8$
 396 is only 1% (Koda & Lien 2013), which suggests limited influence of element-scale
 397 three-dimensionality on the element drag here. More importantly, studies have found that
 398 around 90% of the total mean drag is associated with the shear layers attached to the
 399 cylinder surface, with less dependence on the flow structure in the far wake (e.g. Fiabane,
 400 Gohlke & Cadot 2011). This suggests that the array-scale three-dimensionality behind the
 401 array, far from most of element wakes, has limited influence on the element drag.

402 The influence of three-dimensionality on the drag on a single cylinder near a wall was
 403 limited when E_z has magnitude of 10^{-2} (Jiang *et al.* 2017). In the present study, each
 404 cylinder is confined by surrounding cylinders, which is similar to their scenario. Figure 6
 405 shows that the magnitude of E_z within the array is between 10^{-3} and 10^{-2} for all the

Obstacle arrangement can control flows

Figure 6. Distribution of time-mean spanwise kinetic energy E_z (defined in (3.1)) for an array of 31 cylinders. The four cases are the same in figure 5: (a) CI, (b) KH, (c) SS and (d) VS. Non-zero E_z values are mostly distributed behind the array rather than within the array, indicating the development of three-dimensionality mostly behind the array.

406 regimes. With reference to Jiang *et al.* (2017), the three-dimensionality in the system
 407 should have limited influence on the drag on the array.

408 To further confirm the applicability of 2-D simulations, a comparison of velocity
 409 profiles is made between 3-D and 2-D simulations in figure 7. In the streamwise direction
 410 (figure 7a-d), for all the regimes, the streamwise velocity decreases with x/D in the
 411 upstream of the array and then continuously decreases throughout the array though some
 412 velocity fluctuations are observed due to the flow heterogeneity induced by individual
 413 cylinders; downstream of the array, the velocity shows complex variation but eventually
 414 increases towards the upstream velocity U_∞ . As the flow transits from regime CI to VS,
 415 the transverse profile becomes deeper in the array wake (at $x/D = 1$) (figure 7e-h).

416 Upstream of and within the array ($x/D \leq 0.5$), there is a good agreement between
 417 the streamwise velocity profiles (figure 7a-d), with RMSE $_\Omega$ of \bar{u}/U_∞ between 3-D and
 418 2-D simulations of 0.2 %, 0.3 %, 0.8 % and 3.3 % for the four regimes, respectively. This

Figure 7. Profiles of time-mean streamwise velocity along $y = 0$ in 3-D simulations comparing with 2-D results: (a) CI, (b) KH, (c) SS and (d) VS. Profiles of time-mean streamwise velocity along $x/D = 1$: (e) CI, (f) KH, (g) SS and (h) VS. Whilst there is good agreement of velocity profiles upstream of and within the array, there are differences in the velocity profiles downstream of the array due to the generation of 3-D flow structures behind the array.

419 suggests that the flow upstream of and within the array modelled in the 2-D simulation is
 420 representative of that in the 3-D simulation.

421 Downstream of the array ($x/D > 0.5$), the level of agreement between 3-D and 2-D
 422 results depends on the regime. In regime CI, the profiles in 3-D and 2-D simulations
 423 are in excellent agreement for both streamwise and transverse profiles (see figure 7a,e),
 424 respectively with $RMSE_{\Omega} = 1.8\%$ and 1.0% . In regimes KH and SS, 3-D and 2-D
 425 transverse profiles agree reasonably well (see figure 7f,g), both with $RMSE_{\Omega}$ less than
 426 3.0% . However, 3-D and 2-D streamwise profiles have similar variation trends along the
 427 wake but different values, with higher $RMSE_{\Omega} = 12.7\%$ and 31.3% for regimes KH and
 428 SS respectively (figure 7b,c). In regime VS (figure 7d,h), both streamwise and transverse
 429 profiles in 2-D simulations follow the same variation trends as these in the 3-D simulation
 430 though noticeable differences in values of \bar{u}/U_{∞} are observed, with $RMSE_{\Omega} = 33.4\%$
 431 and 22.4% , respectively.

432 The differences in values of \bar{u}/U_∞ downstream of the array are generated due to the
 433 following reasons. Firstly, due to missing turbulent diffusion in the 2-D simulation, the
 434 2-D vortex structures in the array wake persist in strength as **they travel** downstream (not
 435 shown) and hence cause stronger wake entrainment. The streamwise velocity is in turn
 436 recovered in a faster rate relative to that in the 3-D simulation. This faster rate becomes
 437 obvious when large-scale 3-D vortex structures are generated at the wake centreline
 438 (comparing **figures 7b–d** and **5b–d**). Furthermore, without vortex stretching 2-D array
 439 shear layers are much stronger and interact to form vortex shedding closer to the array (not
 440 shown), which hence induces wake entrainment earlier than in the 3-D simulation. This is
 441 consistent with earlier recovery of \bar{u}/U_∞ in the streamwise profile (see **figure 7c,d**).

442 The focus of the present study is arrangement effects on the bulk flow through and bulk
 443 drag on the array, which are associated with the variation of element-scale flow and drag
 444 characteristics with arrangement (demonstrated **later**). Therefore, no further attempt was
 445 made to demonstrate the differences in the array wake between 2-D and 3-D simulations.

446 The discussions based on **figures 5–7** as a combination **suggest** that 2-D simulations
 447 may be a reasonable tool that helps us increase the resolution of the parameter space
 448 in investigating the arrangement effects on the drag on the array elements and the bulk
 449 velocity through the array, though caution is needed in interpretation of 2-D array-scale
 450 wake.

3.2. Arrangement effects: gap ratio and array-to-element diameter ratio

451 To interpret the arrangement effects at the element scale, a first step is to understand the
 452 element-scale flow and drag characteristics within a finite circular array. Since the array
 453 is a combination of multiple lines of cylinders, therefore, to help the understanding, the
 454 scenario of flow past a line of cylinders is studied first.

455 The key findings of flow past a single line of cylinders from existing literature (Hosseini
 456 *et al.* 2020; Zhu *et al.* 2021; Eizadi *et al.* 2022) can be summarised as: (i) the flow evolution
 457 along the line is chiefly controlled by G/d when $Re_d \leq 200$ and $N \geq 3$; (ii) the flow transits
 458 from **SLR** to **TRS** occurring **at** $G/d \approx 3.7$; **and** (iii) **SLR** and **TRS** can cause significant
 459 drag reduction to the elements covered by these characteristic flow structures.

460 Two typical cases at $G/d = 2$ and 4.5 with $N = 11$ from 3-D simulations are used to
 461 illustrate the two characteristic flow structures and drag reduction mechanism associated
 462 with them (see cross-sectional flow fields in **figure 8**). It is seen that the flow for $G/d = 2$
 463 remains 2-D, while the flow is 3-D for $G/d = 4.5$. For $G/d = 2$ (see **figure 8a**) the two
 464 (positive, negative) separated shear layers from the upstream cylinder reattach on the
 465 downstream cylinder from C2 to C3 and the **SLR** develops downstream into regular vortex
 466 shedding; these vortices develop a unique pattern downstream where the positive and
 467 negative vortices are separated into two parallel rows spanning from C8 to C11, i.e. **TRS**.
 468 For $G/d = 4.5$ (**figure 8b**), von Kármán vortices develop from C1; these vortices develop
 469 **TRS** downstream spanning from C2 to C4. Further downstream the flow becomes chaotic.

470 In the wake of a single cylinder, the primary von Kármán vortices were found to develop
 471 downstream into **TRS** when $L_y/L_x > 0.365$, where L_y is the cross-wake spacing between
 472 centres of positive and negative wake vortices and L_x is the distance between centres of
 473 adjacent vortices of the same sign (vortex centre is defined by the maximum of spanwise
 474 vorticity $\omega_z d/U_\infty$). This threshold has been theoretically identified based on inviscid
 475 theory and validated through both experiments (Durgin & Karlsson 1971; Karasudani
 476 & Funakoshi 1994) and numerical simulations (Thompson *et al.* 2014). In the present
 477 study, **TRS** is similarly developed from primary von Kármán vortices from C1 in a line.

Figure 8. Flow and drag characteristics of a single line of 11 cylinders for $\theta = 0^\circ$ in 3-D DNS. Instantaneous cross-sectional ($z/D = 0$) flow fields for $G/d = 2$ (a) and $G/d = 4.5$ (b). (c) Distribution of drag coefficient along the line. Cylinders with TRS or SLR (marked in dark grey in a–c).

479 Therefore, this threshold $L_y/L_x > 0.365$ is adopted here to quantitatively classify the TRS,
 480 with the two length scales L_y, L_x illustrated in figure 8(a).

481 The distribution of drag coefficient along the line for the two gap ratios are plotted in
 482 figure 8(c). It is seen that the cylinders within either SLR (C2, C3, C8–C11 marked in dark
 483 grey in figure 8a) or TRS (C2–C4 in figure 8b) have very small drag coefficients relative
 484 to other cylinders without these typical flow structures.

485 Figure 9 illustrates how the characteristic element-scale wake varies with increasing G/d
 486 (and hence D/d) for a circular array with a fixed total number of cylinders ($N = 109$) in 3-D
 487 DNS. The element-scale wake structure within a multiple-line array exhibits three flow
 488 states: (i) SLR develops for a number of cylinders within an array; (ii) the element-scale
 489 wake in the array is characterised by TRS, which covers at least two cylinders within a line;
 490 and (iii) over the entire array no downstream cylinders are within a region of TRS or SLR
 491 (termed ‘non-covered’, or NOC, here). Two cases with SLR are presented in figure 9(a,b).
 492 For $(G/d, D/d) = (2, 22.2)$ (figure 9a), SLR fully occupies the three lines of cylinders in
 493 the middle of the array (lines $1^-, 0, 1^+$). The SLR is progressively broken down as the
 494 array edges are approached (figure 9a). The resultant wakes of individual cylinders remain
 495 steady but are formed into a staggered pattern. The formation of the staggered pattern
 496 is attributed to flow diversion towards either side of the array, as indicated by diverging
 497 streamlines (figure 9a). At larger $G/d = 2.5$, SLR can develop downstream into vortex
 498 shedding (lines $2^-, 1^-, 0, 1^+, 2^+$ in figure 9b). With further increases in G/d , it is seen
 499 that the state TRS characterises a number of cylinders (figure 9c). The TRS covers from
 500 C3 to C5 in four lines (the filled circles in lines $2^-, 1^-, 1^+, 2^+$) and up to C6 in the
 501 middle line (line 0). Finally, state NOC is observed for the array with the largest $G/d = 8$
 502 (figure 9d), where the TRS is confined between C2 and C3 in the three lines ($0, 1^-, 2^-$)

Obstacle arrangement can control flows

Figure 9. Cross-sectional instantaneous flow field (at $z/D=0$) for arrays of 109 cylinders with various gap ratios in 3-D DNS. Cylinder lines are numbered, and the cylinders covered by TRS are marked in dark grey in (c,d), which is classified based on the criterion $L_y/L_x > 0.365$. With increasing G/d , the extent of elements covered by SLR or TRS over the array is reduced.

503 without covering any downstream cylinder in each line. With increasing G/d , the SLR or
 504 TRS covers a smaller number of cylinders within a line (see figure 9a–d).

505 Flow transition processes similar to those of a single line of cylinders are observed
 506 in flow through multiple-line arrays. A transition from SLR to vortex shedding is seen
 507 in both a single line and an array for small gap ratio (figures 8a and 9b); for large gap
 508 ratio, a downstream transition from primary vortex to secondary vortex and eventually to
 509 chaotic wake is observed in both the single line and the array. Comparisons of spectra of

Figure 10. Similarity of downstream evolution of the lift coefficient spectrum and instantaneous flow between an array of 109 cylinders and a single line of 11 cylinders (both at $G/d = 8$) in 3-D DNS. Here ‘P’ and ‘S’ represent primary and secondary frequencies, which are indicative of the element-scale primary vortex and secondary vortex, respectively.

510 lift coefficient combined with the instantaneous flow field for the array ($G/d = 8$, $N = 109$)
 511 with those of the counterpart single line case are used to demonstrate this (see figure 10).
 512 The flow and lift spectra for different lines show similar evolution along the line, such that
 513 only lines 0 and 4^- are presented for demonstration. The primary frequency dominates
 514 the first two cylinders in each line within the array (figure 10 a_1, a_2, c_1, c_2). This shows
 515 that the von Kármán vortex shed from C1 governs the frequency of the TRS occurring
 516 behind C2 (see figure 10 b). The secondary frequency emerges on the spectrum of C2
 517 and then becomes dominant over C3 to C6 (figure 10 a_3-a_7, c_3-c_7). Further downstream,
 518 no dominant frequency is observed (figure 10 a_8, c_8), which characterises the chaotic flow
 519 (see figure 10 b, d). Such downstream evolution of lift spectrum and vortex structures is
 520 similar to that for the single line (see figure 10 e_1-e_8, f), demonstrating the similarity of
 521 flow evolution within the array to that for a single line of cylinders.

522 Similarity is also seen in the distribution of drag coefficients of cylinders along the
 523 line. This is demonstrated in figure 11 for an array of cylinders with $N = 109$, $G/d = 4.5$,
 524 for which the instantaneous flow field is shown in figure 9(c). It is seen that the drag
 525 distributions along lines of cylinders are very similar to that of the single line especially
 526 in the middle of the array (comparing figure 11 with figure 8c), with a sharp decrease of $\overline{C_{d,i}}$
 527 through the first three cylinders, followed by a decrease and an increase over downstream
 528 cylinders.

529 The variation of $\overline{C_{d,i}}$ along each row of cylinders within the array in 2-D simulations
 530 follows the trend of that in 3-D simulations. Values of $\overline{C_{d,i}}$ for some cylinders in 3-D

Obstacle arrangement can control flows

Figure 11. Distribution of drag coefficient of cylinders within an array of cylinders with $N = 109$, $G/d = 4.5$ in both 3-D and 2-D DNS. The cross-sectional instantaneous flow field for this case is shown in figure 9(c). The distributions of $\overline{C_{d,i}}$ along the line of cylinders within the array in both 3-D and 2-D simulations are similar to that of the single line of cylinders shown in figure 8(c), especially in the middle of the array, suggesting the applicability of using 2-D DNS in characterising the element drag.

531 simulations are slightly lower than those in 2-D simulations. For all the cases in the present
 532 study, the RMSE between 3-D and 2-D $\overline{C_{d,i}}$ values RMSE_{Ω} is less than 8%. This level
 533 of discrepancy of $\overline{C_{d,i}}$ between 3-D and 2-D simulations is comparable to that of flow
 534 past two tandem cylinders [e.g. Koda & Lien 2013]. This demonstrates the minor effect of
 535 using the 2-D assumption to simulate the flow within the present scope.

536 Despite the similarity, the presence of the adjacent lines of cylinders in proximity in
 537 arrays makes the flow evolution along a line within the array more complicated than
 538 that along the single line. The adjacent lines have two effects on the flow: (i) adjacent
 539 lines behave similarly to bounding walls (Zdravkovich 1997; Sahin & Owens 2004) to
 540 confine the flow motions in the cross-flow direction, termed confinement effect, and (ii)
 541 vortices shed from adjacent lines interact with each other (vortex interaction), destroying
 542 the regular vortex structures. The first effect is illustrated by comparing the instantaneous
 543 flow field between the single line and the lines within the array for the same $G/d = 2$.
 544 For the single-line case (figure 8a), the flow develops downstream from SLR to vortex
 545 shedding. In contrast, the flows along three lines within the array (1^- , 0 , 1^+ in figure 9a)
 546 are stabilised with SLR persisting throughout the array due to the confinement of adjacent
 547 lines of cylinders.

548 A consequence of influences of adjacent lines is a more chaotic flow within the array,
 549 in comparison with that along the single line of cylinders. For a line of cylinders, a
 550 distinct low frequency ($fd/U_{\infty} = 0.035$) is observed from C4 to C8 (see figure 10a₄–a₈).
 551 This frequency corresponds to the large-scale tertiary vortex reported in Eizadi *et al.*
 552 (2022). This is, however, absent for the array (figure 10a₄–a₈, c₄–c₈) where the flow
 553 exhibits a chaotic shedding feature (see figure 10b,d). This is, however, absent for the array
 554 (figure 10a₄–a₈) where the flow exhibits a chaotic shedding feature (see figure 10b,d).

555 In addition to the influence of adjacent lines, flow through an array is more complex still
 556 than that of a single line due to the diversion of flow around the array. With this diverted
 557 flow, element wakes (particularly near array edges) are directed laterally towards the edge
 558 of the array, as shown by streamlines in figure 8(a). Hence typical flow structures such
 559 as SLR and the TRS, formed due to the alignment of element wakes with the incident
 560 flow, progressively break down as array edges are approached (figure 8a–d). This is the
 561 reason why the drag distribution along a line of cylinders increasingly deviates from that
 562 of a single line of cylinders as moving from the array middle towards its edge (comparing
 563 figure 11 with figure 8c).

564 The identified characteristic flow structures, SLR and the TRS, play important roles
 565 in determining $\overline{C_d}$. A plot of $\overline{C_d}$ for arrays with $N = 31$ (figure 12a), combined with the
 566 cross-sectional instantaneous flow fields in 3-D simulations for critical G/d (figure 12b–d),
 567 is used to demonstrate this. It is seen that with increasing G/d , $\overline{C_d}$ generally increases
 568 towards an asymptotic value of roughly 0.8 (figure 12a). The variation of $\overline{C_d}$ with G/d
 569 in 3-D simulations is close to that in 2-D simulations. Therefore, 2-D simulations are
 570 employed to increase the resolution of parameter range of G/d , which gives the critical
 571 values ($\approx 3.3, 7.8$) for the transition between different regimes. Despite the general
 572 increasing trend, the variation of $\overline{C_d}$ with G/d depends on the element-scale flow structure.
 573 Shear-layer reattachment remains dominant in the range $G/d = 1.8\text{--}2.7$ (figure 12a), with
 574 typical instantaneous flow field shown in figure 12(b). There is therefore little variation
 575 of $\overline{C_d}$ in this range (figure 12a). Beyond $G/d = 2.7$, SLR starts to break down. With
 576 diminished drag reduction in SLR, the $\overline{C_d}$ value increases sharply above $G/d = 2.7$. With
 577 further increase in G/d , the TRS begins to dominate the element wake. The extent of
 578 cylinders covered by TRS is virtually unchanged over the range $G/d = 3.4\text{--}4.7$, in which
 579 the instantaneous flow field is similar to that shown in figure 12(c) and hence the $\overline{C_d}$
 580 value stabilises around 0.55. There is a second sharp increase of $\overline{C_d}$ from $G/d = 4.7$ to 8
 581 where with increasing G/d the extent of cylinders covered by TRS in a line is progressively
 582 reduced upstream and eventually to only C2 for lines in the middle of the array (see
 583 figure 12d). The element wake is in state NOC for $G/d > 8$, causing the near-constant
 584 value of $\overline{C_d}$ for $G/d > 8$ (figure 12a). The above interpretation reveals the underlying link
 585 between the characteristic flow structure (and its variation with G/d) and the averaged
 586 element drag coefficient in finite arrays.

587 More arrays with $N = 7, 19, 31, 55, 109$ were simulated to demonstrate these three states
 588 (SLR, TRS, NOC) in the $(G/d, D/d)$ parameter space (figure 13). This figure includes 10
 589 3-D cases, with complement of 73 2-D cases due to the computational cost. It is seen from
 590 figure 13 that the element-scale wake structures in 3-D and 2-D simulations are in the same
 591 flow state for the same value of G/d and D/d . The element-scale wake structure is primarily
 592 set by G/d in most cases. For small gap ratio, SLR dominates the element wake within
 593 an array at $G/d \lesssim 3$, whose threshold is less than that for the single line ($G/d \lesssim 3.7$).
 594 For intermediate gap ratio ($3 \lesssim G/d \lesssim 8$), the element-scale wake is characterised by
 595 TRS. Cases with large gap ratio ($G/d \gtrsim 8$) display state NOC. With increasing G/d , the
 596 transition from SLR into TRS coincides with the decrease in the extent of cylinders within
 597 an array covered by SLR, as shown in figure 9(a–c). Similar decreasing trend is observed
 598 for the extent of TRS as the flow transits from TRS to NOC (figure 9c,d). The reduction
 599 in the extent of these two characteristic flow structures in an array with increasing G/d is
 600 similar to that observed for the single-line scenarios (e.g. Hosseini *et al.* 2020).

601 For a single line (e.g. Eizadi *et al.* 2022) and an infinite array (da Silva *et al.* 2019)
 602 of cylinders, the formation of characteristic element-scale flow feature is controlled by
 603 the gap ratio when the cylinder Reynolds number is fixed. It appears that this is also

Obstacle arrangement can control flows

Figure 12. Demonstration of the critical role of the element-scale flow structures in determining the average element drag coefficient in both 3-D and 2-D DNS. (a) Variation of $\overline{C_d}$ with G/d for arrays with $N = 31$. Dashed lines represent the range of G/d where SLR, TRS or NOC becomes dominant. (b-d) Cross-sectional instantaneous flow fields of $N = 31$ for critical gap ratios ($G/d = 2.7, 4.5, 8$) at $z/D = 0$ in 3-D simulations shown in (a). In (c,d) cylinders covered by TRS are marked in dark grey. Despite the general increasing trend of $\overline{C_d}$, values of $\overline{C_d}$ are controlled by the characteristic flow structure and its variation with G/d .

604 the case for a finite circular array when $D/d > 10$, as shown by the separation of three
 605 characteristic element-scale wake states at two virtually invariant G/d values (3, 8) for
 606 $N \gtrsim 31$ in figure 13. This suggests that the array-scale (D/d) has secondary influence on the
 607 formation of characteristic element-scale wake if the array has sufficiently large number
 608 of cylinders ($N \gtrsim 31$) and large size ($D/d \gtrsim 10$).

609 Figure 13 also illustrates that the averaged element drag coefficient $\overline{C_d}$ (the filled colour
 610 in each symbol) increases with G/d but decreases with D/d , meaning that larger and denser
 611 arrays have lower average drag coefficients. The $\overline{C_d}$ value varies significantly with G/d and
 612 D/d by a factor of more than 4 (from 0.23 to 0.90) in the numerical runs of this study.

613 3.3. Arrangement effects: incident flow angle

614 Varying the incident flow angle can generate a wide range of element-scale wake
 615 structures, and hence drag distributions, over an array. This is demonstrated through 3-D
 616 DNS by varying the incident flow angle for an array of cylinders with $N = 31$ and $G/d = 4.5$
 617 in figure 14. For $\theta = 0^\circ$, the flow along each line of cylinders develops from von Kármán
 618 vortices into TRS (figure 14a). Channelised flow with streamwise velocity higher than

Figure 13. The element-scale wake structure and average drag coefficient $\overline{C_d}$ of an array of cylinders mapped out in the parameter space of G/d and D/d for $\theta = 0^\circ$ for both 3-D and 2-D DNS. Cases along each dashed line have the same total number of cylinders in the array (N , marked on the right). Cases with the same flow state cluster together, demonstrating dependence of characteristic element-scale flow feature on G/d and D/d . The $\overline{C_d}$ value varies significantly with G/d and D/d from 0.23 to 0.90, highlighting the significant impact of cylinder arrangement.

619 the ambient velocity is formed between adjacent lines (figure 14b). In contrast, the mean
 620 velocity in the gap between cylinders in each line is extremely low (figure 14b). The
 621 formation of TRS coincides with suppression of lateral mixing (Durgin & Karlsson 1971),
 622 which causes the persistence of channelised flow with high velocity throughout the array.
 623 The suppression of lateral mixing is indicated by very low Reynolds shear stress magnitude
 624 around covered cylinders (marked with dark grey circles in figure 14c). Accordingly, the
 625 low gap velocity leads to very low drag force on the cylinders covered by TRS (figure 14d).

626 For the case with $\theta = 10^\circ$, the TRS is identifiable in the lower half of the array but
 627 completely disappears in the upper half of the array (figure 14e). In the lower half, the
 628 flow diversion (towards the lower side) helps to direct the local flow along the geometric
 629 channels resulting in the formation of channelised flow. The diverging flow, however, cuts
 630 across the channel direction in the upper half and suppresses channelised flow, such that
 631 most cylinders in the upper half are no longer in the low-velocity wake regions of upstream
 632 cylinders (figure 14f). The forces on most of the cylinders are therefore increased and at a
 633 significant angle to the primary axis of the line (figure 14h).

634 For $\theta = 30^\circ$, the TRS and channelised flow completely disappear within the array
 635 (figure 14i-k), which leads to a significant increase in mean drag coefficient (figure 14l).
 636 The flow progressively develops downstream into a chaotic state, as evidenced by the
 637 vorticity field in figure 14(i) and the absence of a dominant peak in spectra of lift
 638 coefficient (not shown). These chaotic vortices cause stronger lateral mixing in comparison
 639 with the other two flow angles (comparing Reynolds shear stress in figure 14c,g,k).
 640 Accordingly, the wake deficit of each cylinder is recovered more rapidly than at smaller
 641 θ (comparing figure 14b,f,j). Any downstream cylinder is in turn out of the low-velocity

Obstacle arrangement can control flows

Figure 14. The variation with incident flow angle of the fields of cross-sectional instantaneous spanwise vorticity (first row) (at $z/D=0$), time-averaged streamwise velocity (second row), Reynolds shear stress (third row) and time-mean force with drag coefficient (fourth row) for an array of 31 cylinders with $(G/d, D/d) = (4.5, 24.8)$ in 3-D DNS. The fields of Reynolds stress and mean flow are post-processed on a time-mean spanwise-average flow field. The first ($a-d$), second ($e-h$) and third ($i-l$) columns represent $\theta = 0^\circ, 10^\circ$ and 30° , respectively. Cylinders within the IRS are marked in dark grey in (a, c, e, g). The arrow in the top-right corner of (d, h, l) represents a unit time-mean force of 1. With increasing θ , the IRS in (a) and channelised flow in (b) are progressively suppressed, which creates an increase in mean drag coefficient in (d, h, l).

Figure 15. Cross-sectional instantaneous flow field (upper half) (at $z/D=0$) and mean field of streamwise velocity (bottom half) for (a) $\theta = 0^\circ$ and (b) $\theta = 30^\circ$ in an array of 109 cylinders ($G/d, D/d$) = (4.5, 48.6) in 3-D DNS. The mean flow is post-processed on a spanwise-average flow field. The colour bar (not shown) of spanwise vorticity is the same as that used in figure 14. **With** increasing θ from 0° to 30° , the breakdown of **TRS** and channelised flow impacts relatively fewer cylinders in a large array relative to that **in** the smaller array in figure 14.

642 region behind its upstream cylinder (figure 14j) and hence has large drag (figure 14l). The
 643 resultant average drag coefficient $\overline{C_d}$ increases, more specifically by 42 %, compared with
 644 that at $\theta = 0^\circ$ (see the legends in figure 14d,l).

645 The incident flow angle becomes less important with **increasing** array diameter for
 646 a fixed gap ratio. This is illustrated by two arrays with $D/d = 24.8$ (figure 14) and
 647 48.6 (figure 15) with the same value of G/d (4.5). The fraction of elements within the
 648 **TRS** decreases from 45 % (figure 14a) to only 14 % when doubling the array diameter
 649 (figure 15a). Consistently, the channelised flow is eliminated near the back of the larger
 650 array (figure 15a), in contrast to that persisting throughout the smaller array (figure 14b).
 651 As indicated by the instantaneous and mean flow fields in figure 15, for the large array,
 652 whilst no channelised flow is formed at $\theta = 30^\circ$, a large number of cylinders form chaotic
 653 vortex shedding ($\sim 39\%$, identified from lift coefficient spectra) and are non-channelised.
 654 Therefore, when increasing θ from 0° to 30° , the resultant breakdown of **TRS** and
 655 channelised flow impacts fewer cylinders within the larger array.

656 With diminished dominance of **TRS** and channelised flow, the total drag on the
 657 larger array becomes less sensitive to θ . This is best indicated by a transverse-averaged
 658 drag coefficient $\langle C_d \rangle_x$, which is the average drag coefficient of elements with identical
 659 streamwise (x) but different transverse (y) locations. It is seen that for the smaller array
 660 ($D/d = 24.8$), $\langle C_d \rangle_x$ for $\theta = 0^\circ$ is largely lower than that for $\theta = 30^\circ$ (figure 16a). A similar
 661 contrast in $\langle C_d \rangle_x$ is seen in the larger array in the same region of $0 < (x - x_0)/d < 25$
 662 (figure 16b), with x_0 the coordinate of the front cylinder in the array. Lower values of
 663 $\langle C_d \rangle_x$ for $\theta = 0^\circ$ in both the small and large arrays **are** associated with the development
 664 of channelised flow **in theregion** $0 < (x - x_0)/d < 25$ (see figures 14b and 15a). The flow
 665 channelisation leads to cylinders in each line largely behaving as a single bluff body and
 666 hence imposing smaller drag forces. This difference in $\langle C_d \rangle_x$ between $\theta = 0^\circ$ **and** 30° is
 667 dramatically diminished (and reverses in sign) downstream of $(x - x_0)/d = 25$ within the
 668 larger array (figure 16b). This is because the channelised flow is progressively eliminated
 669 beyond $(x - x_0)/d = 25$ in the large array at $\theta = 0^\circ$, which coincides with cylinders in

Obstacle arrangement can control flows

Figure 16. Evolution of the transverse-averaged drag coefficient $\langle C_d \rangle_x$ along the two arrays for incident flow angles $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 30° in 3-D DNS. The two arrays shown in (a,b) have the same value of G/d (4.5) but different values of D/d : (a) $D/d = 24.8, N = 31$; (b) $D/d = 48.6, N = 109$. Error bars represent the standard error of the C_d values averaged in the transverse (y) direction. Both arrays have a dependence of $\langle C_d \rangle_x$ on θ in the region $0 < (x - x_0)/d < 25$. The larger array has minimal dependence on incident flow angle beyond $(x - x_0)/d = 25$.

670 this region subject to higher local velocity (comparing figure 15a). Near either side of
 671 the array where flow diversion is strong, the cylinders beyond $(x - x_0)/d = 25$ at $\theta = 0^\circ$
 672 even experience higher velocity than at $\theta = 30^\circ$ (comparing figure 15a,b). This leads to
 673 greater $C_{d,i}$ values for cylinders at $(x - x_0)/d > 25$ than $\theta = 30^\circ$. This reversal of $\langle C_d \rangle_x$ at
 674 $(x - x_0)/d = 25$ explains why the averaged drag coefficient \bar{C}_d for the larger array is much
 675 less dependent on incident flow angle (values provided in figure 16 legends).

676 The incident flow angle effects are sensitive to the gap ratio. This is demonstrated
 677 by comparing the case of $G/d = 2.7$ with that of $G/d = 4.5$ described above. At $\theta = 0^\circ$
 678 instantaneous flow within the array is dominated by SLR (figure 17a) and channelised
 679 flow develops throughout the array (figure 17b). All cylinders in turn have very low drag
 680 except for the most upstream cylinder in each line (figure 17c). Shear layer reattachment
 681 breaks down into vortex shedding for some cylinders for $\theta = 10^\circ$ (figure 17d), with incident
 682 flow redirected to pass through the gap between adjacent lines of cylinders (figure 17e). For
 683 $\theta = 30^\circ$, SLR is completely suppressed, and the flow is characterised by a staggered steady
 684 wake pattern (figure 17g). Clearly, with increasing θ , the channel flow is progressively
 685 broken down from the top of the array towards its bottom. The average drag coefficient is
 686 increased by 15% with an increase of θ from 0° to 30° , which is smaller than 42% for the
 687 case with $G/d = 4.5$ (comparing legends between figures 14d,l and 17c,i).

Figure 17. The variation of cross-sectional instantaneous flow field (first row) (at $z/D = 0$), time-averaged field of streamwise velocity (second row) and the distribution of force and drag coefficient (third row) with incident flow angle for an array of 31 cylinders with $(G/d, D/d) = (2.7, 15.3)$ in 3-D DNS. The first (a-c), second (d-f) and third (g-i) columns represent $\theta = 0^\circ$, 10° and 30° , respectively. The colour bar of spanwise vorticity omitted in (a,d,g) is the same as in figure 14. With increasing θ , SLR in (a) and channelised flow in (b) within the array are progressively suppressed, which coincides with an increase in drag on cylinders over the array in (c,f,i).

688 In combination, figures 14–17 indicate that the variation of $\overline{C_d}$ with θ is dependent on
 689 both the gap ratio and array-to-element diameter ratio. This strong, nonlinear dependence
 690 of $\overline{C_d}$ on θ is further demonstrated in figure 18 with a combination of 3-D and 2-D
 691 simulations. Generally, the influence of incident flow angle on $\overline{C_d}$ become less significant
 692 with decreasing G/d for a fixed total number of cylinders N . On varying θ from 0° to
 693 30° , the averaged drag coefficient can vary in a wide range. For instance, the $\overline{C_d}$ value
 694 varies in the ranges of 0.90–1.30 and 0.55–0.78 for the arrays with $(G/d, D/d) = (17, 35)$,
 695 (4.5, 24.8), respectively (denoted in order ‘ \diamond ’, ‘ \square ’ in figure 18). All arrays exhibit their
 696 lowest value of $\overline{C_d}$ at $\theta = 0^\circ$ due to the formation of channelised flow at this angle (e.g.
 697 figures 14b, 15a and 17b). However, the highest value of $\overline{C_d}$ occurs at a range of angles
 698 and the averaged drag coefficient does not necessarily increase with θ monotonically. It is
 699 therefore insufficient to infer the variation of $\overline{C_d}$ with θ based purely on the positioning of
 700 cylinders relative to incident flow or the projected area of cylinders normal to the incident
 701 flow. The controlling mechanism for the dependence of $\overline{C_d}$ on θ is the complex variation
 702 of element-scale wake interaction with the cylinder arrangement.

Obstacle arrangement can control flows

Figure 18. The strong, nonlinear variation of \bar{C}_d with θ across the range of arrays, demonstrating that the \bar{C}_d value is not only related to the array geometry but also depends on the orientation of the array. Note that the symbols with red and black edges represent 3-D and 2-D cases, respectively.

3.4. Universal descriptor of bulk flow through a porous array

In §§ 3.2 and 3.3, we have shown that the element-scale flow and drag characteristics can vary widely with arrangement parameters G/d , D/d and θ . However, none of these parameters independently control flow through the porous array. From the perspective of momentum balance, the bulk flow through a porous array is controlled by the array resistance, which is defined by the effective flow blockage parameter Γ'_D (Chang & Constantinescu 2015). It is therefore hypothesised that the effective flow blockage parameter provides a universal description of bulk bleeding flow, which is demonstrated in this section.

Figure 19 presents the variation of \bar{u}_p/U_∞ with Γ_D and Γ'_D with incorporating results from both 3-D and 2-D simulations. The RMSE $_{\Omega}$ of \bar{u}_p/U_∞ for the same values of Γ_D between 3-D and 2-D simulations is 2%. Given this small discrepancy, the following discussion is based on a combination of 3-D and 2-D simulations.

We first examine the variation of bulk bleeding velocity \bar{u}_p/U_∞ , defined in (2.7), with the geometric flow blockage parameter Γ_D (assuming $\bar{C}_d = 1$) as it has been used to describe the bleeding flow in the literature (e.g. Rominger & Nepf 2011; Zong & Nepf 2012). It is seen that the bleeding velocity generally decreases with increasing Γ_D . As per (2.13), this means that a denser (low G/d), larger (high D/d) array typically has a lower bleeding velocity.

Despite the general decreasing trend, the bleeding velocity is not entirely controlled by Γ_D . Data from the same arrays (and thus the same value of Γ_D) but with different arrangements are highly scattered, especially in the intermediate range of Γ_D . For instance, figure 19(a) incorporates ten typical arrays with different θ from 0° to 30° with a constant increment of 5° , spanning across the investigated Γ_D range (see grey filled symbols). The difference between the maximum and minimum of \bar{u}_p/U_∞ in the range of $\theta = 0^\circ$ – 30° is only about 0.02 for a very small or large flow blockage parameter (e.g. $\Gamma_D = 0.3$, 24.2). In contrast, for a medium $\Gamma_D = 1.8$, this difference can be even up to 0.15, which is one order of magnitude higher than that for very small or very large Γ_D . By varying G/d , D/d and θ (between 0° – 30°) simultaneously but keeping $\Gamma_D = 1.8$, the absolute velocity difference between the maximal and minimal values can be even 0.28 and the relative difference is

Figure 19. The relationship between the bleeding velocity \bar{u}_p/U_∞ and flow blockage parameters. Here $\bar{C}_d = 1$ and direct measurement of \bar{C}_d are used in (a) Γ_D and (b) Γ'_D . The filled symbols in different colours represent the cases varying θ from 0° to 30° with an interval of 5° (see table 4 in Appendix B). The data points are scattered in (a) but collapse well in (b), demonstrating that Γ'_D controls the bulk bleeding flow.

733 50 % (cases 8 and 33 in table 4 in Appendix B). These demonstrate that the impact of
 734 the cylinder arrangement on bleeding flow is most critical in the intermediate range of
 735 Γ_D , particularly in the range $1 \lesssim \Gamma_D \lesssim 3$ where the difference between the minimum and
 736 maximum of \bar{u}_p , associated with variation of θ from 0° to 30° , is greater than 10 % of
 737 U_∞ . The high scattering of data demonstrates that the cylinder arrangement can impose a
 738 first-order influence on the bleeding flow. The incompleteness of Γ_D in defining bleeding
 739 flow is because this parameter only defines the geometric bulk blockage of an array without
 740 fully incorporating information of arrangement.

741 The prevalence of the characteristic flow structures appears to be the underlying physical
 742 mechanism for the most critical arrangement effects in the intermediate range of Γ_D (1–3).

743 It is found that this range of Γ_D corresponds to the intermediate range of G/d and D/d
 744 where the **TRS** and **SLR** is the dominant flow feature within an array (see [figure 13](#)). With
 745 small variation in θ , the extent of the **TRS** or **SLR** within the array (and the associated
 746 reduction in drag) can be greatly enhanced or suppressed. Accordingly, $\overline{C_d}$ (and thus
 747 \bar{u}_p/U_∞) can be particularly sensitive to θ . Outside this range, the flow within the array
 748 is characterised by either non-covered element-scale wake (NOC) (low Γ_D) or very low
 749 local velocity (hence low drag) (high Γ_D); the bleeding flow is therefore less dependent
 750 on the cylinder arrangement.

751 Contrastingly, there is excellent collapse of bleeding flow data with the effective flow
 752 blockage parameter Γ'_D using direct measurement of $\overline{C_d}$ ([figure 19b](#)). In fact, the scattered
 753 data points in the critical range ($1 \lesssim \Gamma_D \lesssim 3$) all collapse in the medium range of
 754 $0.5 \lesssim \Gamma'_D \lesssim 1.5$ where \bar{u}_p/U_∞ has higher gradient against Γ'_D than at the two ends of Γ'_D .
 755 Any change to the cylinder arrangement in this range will alter Γ'_D and hence dramatically
 756 change \bar{u}_p/U_∞ . The improved collapse of \bar{u}_p/U_∞ with Γ'_D demonstrates the importance
 757 of hydrodynamic response of $\overline{C_d}$ to the array arrangement in controlling the bulk bleeding
 758 flow, which is, however, missed in geometric Γ_D . The response is manifested by the
 759 variation of element-scale flow and drag characteristics with arrangement as discussed
 760 in §§ 3.2 and 3.3. By allowing the controlling influence of array arrangement on $\overline{C_d}$, the
 761 effective flow blockage parameter, i.e. Γ'_D , not only controls the amount of flow passing
 762 through a porous array but also determines when the arrangement effects are critical.

763 There is vast variability of element-scale flow characteristics in Γ'_D . For instance,
 764 the two 3-D cases 13* and 20* (marked in **bold** text in [table 4](#)) with $\Gamma'_D \approx 1.5$ have
 765 different element-scale flow structures but almost identical values of $\bar{u}_p/U_\infty \approx 0.2$. Vortex
 766 shedding is formed within one array ($G/d = 2.5, D/d = 27.5, N = 109$) at $\theta = 0^\circ$ but not in
 767 the other array ($G/d = 2.3, D/d = 13, N = 31$) at $\theta = 30^\circ$ (see [figure 23a,b](#) in [Appendix B](#)).
 768 The effective flow blockage parameter basically characterises the net bulk resistance of
 769 the array, which determines the bulk bleeding flow. The resistance can be broken down
 770 into discrete point drag forces, which are physically modelled by individual cylinders in a
 771 circular domain herein. Depending on the array and incident flow properties (defined by
 772 $G/d, D/d, \alpha, \theta, Re_d$), the array can have various element-scale flow and drag characteristics
 773 at fixed Γ'_D .

774 [Figure 19\(b\)](#) demonstrates that the bulk bleeding velocity is a function of Γ'_D . We have
 775 demonstrated the complex variation of $\overline{C_d}$, a critical component of Γ'_D , with arrangement,
 776 by varying selected arrangement parameters ($G/d, D/d, \theta$) in §§ 3.2 and 3.3. As a
 777 combination, it shows how the arrangement changes the element-scale flow and drag
 778 characteristics and eventually changes the bulk force on and the bulk flow through the
 779 array. Whilst in a large body of [literature](#) independent variables (e.g. $G/d, D/d, Re_d$) have
 780 been used to define the flow-array system (e.g. [Ball et al. 1996](#); [Chang & Constantinescu](#)
 781 [2015](#); [Cheng et al. 2019](#)), in relatively **fewer** studies **was** the combined flow blockage
 782 **parameter** used as a governing parameter (e.g. [Chen et al. 2012](#)). This paper shows
 783 that the independent parameters and the combined parameter are indeed interdependent,
 784 fundamentally consistent and describe the system at the **element** scale and **array** scale,
 785 respectively.

3.5. Variability of averaged drag coefficient in and with Γ_D

786
 787 The scattering of data points in [figure 19\(a\)](#) is related to the variation of $\overline{C_d}$ for the same
 788 Γ_D (geometric flow blockage). By accounting for the $\overline{C_d}$ variation, [figure 19\(b\)](#) presents a
 789 universal relation between \bar{u}_p/U_∞ and Γ'_D . However, prediction of \bar{u}_p/U_∞ in reality still

Figure 20. (a) A summary of data of \bar{C}_d against Γ_D . (b) List of references shown in (a). The symbols from the present study represent the same cases as shown in the legend in figure 19(a). Note: Exp, laboratory experiment; Num, numerical simulation. The plot in (a) demonstrates that there is variability of \bar{C}_d both in and with Γ_D .

790 requires quantitative information of \bar{C}_d . Therefore, the variability of \bar{C}_d in and with Γ_D
 791 is investigated in figure 20(a), which compiles data from this study and previous work
 792 (listed in figure 20(b)). It is seen that the present data agree with existing data of various
 793 arrangements and Re_d . The $RMSE_{\Omega}$ of \bar{u}_p/U_{∞} for the same values of Γ_D between the
 794 present 3-D and 2-D simulations is 8 %.

795 With increasing Γ_D the averaged drag coefficient generally decreases and variability of
 796 \bar{C}_d in Γ_D reduces. The averaged drag coefficient varies from minimum to maximum by up
 797 to 50 % at low $\Gamma_D = 0.5$, but only by 17 % at $\Gamma_D = 24$ in the range $\theta = 0^{\circ} - 30^{\circ}$. For large
 798 Γ_D , the array can be either very densely packed or very large, which respectively reduces
 799 the freedom of altering arrangement and limits the impact of typical flow structures in
 800 changing arrangement. The overall drag force in turn becomes much less dependent on
 801 arrangement. Instead, it is more dependent on the extremely low bleeding velocity. This
 802 leads to convergence of \bar{C}_d at high Γ_D .

803 Most data in figure 20(a) have \bar{C}_d values much lower than unity, the value adopted in
 804 previous studies (e.g. Zong & Nepf 2012). While $\bar{C}_d = 1$ was assumed with reference to

Obstacle arrangement can control flows

Figure 21. The variations of average root mean square lift and drag coefficients with the effective flow blockage parameter. The symbols represent the same cases as shown in the legend in figure 19(a). Note that the dashed ellipses mark the cases 12* and 19* (table 3 in Appendix B), which have different arrangements but the same value of $\Gamma_D = 3$. The $\overline{C_{d,rms}}$ and $\overline{C_{l,rms}}$ values show a different variation trend with Γ'_D at either side of $\Gamma'_D \approx 1.5$.

805 a single solid cylinder in steady flow, the averaged drag coefficient for a porous array is
 806 normally lower than that for a single cylinder due to arrangement effects. The complex
 807 variation of element-scale flow characteristics with independent variables (G/d , D/d , θ , α ,
 808 Re_d) makes it difficult to collapse those independent parameters down to a single parameter
 809 to accurately characterise $\overline{C_d}$. Nevertheless, figure 20(a) enables a rough estimation of $\overline{C_d}$
 810 for real systems, with uncertainty range for given Γ_D . When combined with figure 19(b),
 811 it provides predictive capacity for the bulk bleeding velocity.

812

3.6. Fluctuating force characteristics

813 In previous sections, force characteristics of individual elements have been discussed
 814 through time-mean quantities (e.g. $\overline{C_d}$). To show the whole picture of element-scale
 815 hydrodynamic features, in this section, the fluctuating components of lift and drag forces
 816 are explored. These two components are quantified by the average root mean squares of lift
 817 and drag coefficients of individual elements, as defined in (2.5). The $RMSE_\Omega$ of $\overline{C_{d,rms}}$
 818 and $\overline{C_{l,rms}}$ for the same values of Γ'_D between the present 3-D and 2-D simulations are 4 %
 819 and 10 %, respectively.

820 The variations of $\overline{C_{d,rms}}$ and $\overline{C_{l,rms}}$ with Γ'_D are associated with both element-scale and
 821 array-scale wake structures (figure 21). With an increase of Γ'_D from 0, the $\overline{C_{d,rms}}$ and
 822 $\overline{C_{l,rms}}$ values increase and peak at $\Gamma'_D \approx 1$ and then decrease sharply to approach zero at
 823 $\Gamma'_D \approx 1.5$. This increasing trend is due to the transition of element-scale wake structure
 824 from the NOC to TRS state with stronger flow fluctuations within the array. In contrast,
 825 beyond $\Gamma'_D \approx 1$, the number of cylinders with element-scale vortex shedding is reduced
 826 with the increase of Γ'_D due to lower bleeding velocity and smaller gaps between individual
 827 elements. This is responsible for the decrease of $\overline{C_{d,rms}}$ and $\overline{C_{l,rms}}$ to 0.

828 In comparison with this decrease, the $\overline{C_{d,rms}}$ and $\overline{C_{l,rms}}$ values start to increase when
 829 $\Gamma'_D \gtrsim 1.5$. Whilst the element-scale vortex shedding is completely suppressed in this Γ'_D
 830 range, the fluctuations of lift and drag forces are driven by flow oscillations induced by
 831 the array-scale vortex structures behind the array. The bleeding velocity is reduced with
 832 the increase of Γ'_D such that the array shear layers become much stronger and the location

833 of generating stronger large-scale vortex structures shifts towards the array. This causes
 834 stronger oscillations to the flow within the array by changing the pressure in the near
 835 wake of the array, which leads to larger fluctuations of lift and drag forces on individual
 836 cylinders.

837 Similar to $\overline{C_d}$ and \bar{u}_p/U_∞ , the $\overline{C_{d,rms}}$ and $\overline{C_{l,rms}}$ values can also vary widely with the
 838 cylinder arrangement, especially in the range of $\Gamma'_D \lesssim 1.5$. For instance, through changing
 839 the cylinder arrangement ($G/d, D/d, \theta$) but keeping $\Gamma_D = 3$, both $\overline{C_{d,rms}}$ and $\overline{C_{l,rms}}$ values
 840 can vary by two orders of magnitude (see 3-D data points denoted by dashed ellipses in
 841 figure 21a,b). Even considering the same value of $\Gamma'_D = 1.2$, the value of $\overline{C_{l,rms}}$ can vary by
 842 a factor of two (from 0.3 up to 0.6). The effective flow blockage parameter Γ'_D controls the
 843 time-mean bulk flow through the array \bar{u}_p/U_∞ but not for the instantaneous flow within
 844 the array (hence $\overline{C_{d,rms}}$ and $\overline{C_{l,rms}}$).

845 4. Discussion

846 Three-dimensional DNS is used to set the benchmark for this work, contributing to major
 847 conclusions. Limited by high computational costs, 2-D DNS served as complement to
 848 further resolve the parameter space. Using 2-D simulations with removing the complexity
 849 of spanwise flow variation allows important element-scale wake interaction patterns on
 850 the x - y plane to be identified that are the key for arrangement effects. Although reasonable
 851 agreement is seen between 2-D and 3-D results of the bulk drag and velocity (see figures 7,
 852 11–13, 19–21), 3-D effects exist in most of the cases, mostly in the array wake behind the
 853 array (as demonstrated in figures 5 and 6). Therefore, 2-D simulations will not be able
 854 to fully characterize wakes of these porous arrays. Since the 3-D effect and turbulence
 855 influence will increase with Reynolds number, 2-D DNS is only valid in modelling flow
 856 through an array of cylinders at relatively low Reynolds number.

857 The identification of controlling influence of arrangement is of practical importance, as
 858 real systems, such as aquatic vegetation, foundation piles and offshore structures, typically
 859 span the most critical range of $1 \lesssim \Gamma_D \lesssim 3$. For instance, kelp forests, seagrasses and
 860 emergent marsh grasses have values of $\Gamma_D \sim O(0.1-10)$ (Rominger & Nepf 2011). The
 861 demonstration of arrangement effects represents a transformation of how to consider the
 862 interaction between flow and a porous obstruction with a large number of elements. To
 863 understand flow through any given porous obstruction, the orientation of its geometry
 864 relative to the incident flow must be known first.

865 Data from existing literature suggest that the arrangement effects are not limited
 866 to the present Reynolds number and array geometry (regular, isotropic configuration
 867 of cylinders). The data in Takemura & Tanaka (2007) showed that the averaged drag
 868 coefficient can be increased by 60% when varying θ from 0° to 45° for an array with
 869 $\alpha = 63.4^\circ$ and $Re_d = 4000$. Similar increasing trend of $\overline{C_d}$ is seen in the data in Zhao *et al.*
 870 (2015) with much lower $Re_d = 100$. In comparison with these regular arrays, the total drag
 871 on a random array can vary by a factor of more than 3, through changing the element
 872 arrangement in an array with fixed array diameter (Nair *et al.* 2023). All these published
 873 results collectively suggest that the arrangement effects still exist for other values of α , Re_d
 874 and random arrays. However, we anticipate that the dependence of element-scale wake
 875 interaction on the cylinder arrangement ($G/d, D/d, \theta, \alpha$) may vary with changes of Re_d
 876 and randomness. Since real systems such as aquatic vegetation can span a wide range of α
 877 and $Re_d \sim O(0-10\,000)$ (e.g. Koch *et al.* 2007; Tanino & Nepf 2008) and elements within
 878 it can be randomly distributed, further work is recommended to explore the arrangement
 879 effects in a wider range of α , Re_d and randomness.

880 **5. Conclusion**

881 This study investigates and confirms the controlling influence of cylinder (element)
 882 arrangement on flow through a circular array of cylinders with DNS, by varying
 883 independent dimensionless arrangement parameters, i.e. gap ratio G/d (in the range
 884 1.2–18), array-to-cylinder diameter ratio D/d (3.6–200) and incident flow angle θ (0° – 30°)
 885 at constant cylinder Reynolds number $Re_d = 200$. The geometric flow blockage parameter
 886 Γ_D , combining the influence of G/d and D/d , spans across the range 0–30. In the parameter
 887 space considered here, 3-D DNS results show that the flow exhibits 3-D features largely in
 888 the array wake behind the array rather than in element wakes within the array.

889 We have demonstrated that the complex variation in local flow and drag characteristics
 890 of individual cylinders within an array is the mechanism for the arrangement effects
 891 on the bulk flow through the array. Element-scale flow structure within an array is
 892 therefore characterised across the full range of G/d and D/d . It is found that at fixed θ
 893 the element-scale flow structure is chiefly controlled by G/d and the influence of the array
 894 scale (D/d) on the formation of characteristic element-scale wake within an array becomes
 895 negligible when the array has enough cylinders ($N \gtrsim 31$) and large size ($D/d \gtrsim 10$).
 896 Specifically, the element wakes over an array are dominated by SLR and TRS for $G/d \lesssim 3$
 897 and for $3 \lesssim G/d \lesssim 8$, respectively. The flow can transit downstream either from SLR to
 898 vortex shedding or from primary vortex (including von Kármán vortex, TRS) to secondary
 899 vortex and eventually to chaotic wake. These flow transition processes are similar to those
 900 observed in flow past a single line of cylinders but with additional complexity due to the
 901 influence of adjacent lines of cylinders within the array and flow diversion towards either
 902 side of the array.

903 For the same Γ_D , with varying the cylinder arrangement (by changing G/d , D/d , θ), the
 904 averaged drag coefficient $\overline{C_d}$ can vary by up to 52 %, the fluctuating components of lift and
 905 drag coefficients $\overline{C_{d,rms}}$ and $\overline{C_{l,rms}}$ can vary by one order of magnitude and the bulk flow
 906 velocity $\overline{u_p}$ through an array can be increased by up to a factor of 2 and 30 % of ambient
 907 velocity. The arrangement effects on $\overline{u_p}$ are most critical at the intermediate range of Γ_D
 908 (1–3). Particularly, in this range, the difference between the minimum and maximum of $\overline{u_p}$,
 909 associated with variation of θ in the range 0° – 30° , is greater than 10 % of U_∞ . The reason
 910 for the critical range is that the extent of TRS or SLR within the array (and the associated
 911 reduction in element drag) can be greatly enhanced or suppressed even with slight change
 912 in arrangement (e.g. θ) in this range. We newly found that the effective flow blockage
 913 parameter Γ'_D using direct measurement of $\overline{C_d}$ controls the bulk velocity $\overline{u_p}$ across the full
 914 range of cylinder arrangements as it allows the controlling influence of array arrangement
 915 on $\overline{C_d}$. The arrays with the same Γ'_D can have very different element-scale flow structures
 916 within an array but the same $\overline{u_p}$. The critical Γ_D range (1–3) falls into the intermediate
 917 range of Γ'_D (0.5–1.5) where the arrangement effects are critical.

918 This paper demonstrates that the modification of bleeding velocity and element-scale
 919 wake interaction can be effectively achieved by altering the element arrangement within
 920 a porous circular array. Arranging elements within the array to $\theta = 0^\circ$ leads to the lowest
 921 drag on the array and hence the highest amount of bulk flow passing through it. At this
 922 typical θ , the lateral mixing around elements covered by characteristic flow structures
 923 (SLR, TRS) is almost fully suppressed. On varying θ to a non-zero degree, the array
 924 drag is increased and hence the bulk flow velocity is reduced. However, the maximum
 925 drag and the minimum bulk flow velocity can occur at a range of θ between 0° and
 926 30° , depending on the element-scale wake interaction within the array. This provides
 927 guidance for the design of engineered structures to maximise or minimise the bulk velocity
 928 through them. Furthermore, the demonstration of controlling influence of arrangement in

Figure 22. Comparison of distribution of pressure coefficient between the present 2-D and 3-D simulations and previous studies. Whilst agreement in (a) validates the resolution of element-scale flow around the individual cylinders, (b) validates the accuracy of resolving the array-scale flow behind the array. (a) $Re_d = 200$ and (b) $Re_D = 1500$.

Figure 23. Comparison of instantaneous flow field between two cases with the same $\Gamma_D' = 1.5$ but different arrangements. Vortex shedding is observed within the large array in (a) but not for the small array in (b). (a) $(G/d, D/d, N, \theta) = (2.5, 27.5, 109, 0^\circ)$ and (b) $(G/d, D/d, N, \theta) = (2.3, 13, 31, 30^\circ)$.

Mesh	Parameters		Hydrodynamic force coefficients		
	N_p	Δt	$\overline{C_{d,16}}$	$\overline{C_{l,rms,16}}$	$\overline{C_d}$
Mesh 1 (reference)	5	0.002	0.1805	0.7104	0.5542
Mesh 2	3	0.002	0.1890 (+4.69 %)	0.7201 (+1.37 %)	0.5564 (+0.39 %)
Mesh 3	7	0.002	0.1879 (+4.06 %)	0.7218 (+1.61 %)	0.5536 (-0.11 %)
Mesh 4	5	0.001	0.1811 (+0.31 %)	0.7123 (+0.28 %)	0.5539 (-0.07 %)

Table 2. Influence of mesh resolution on force coefficients for $N = 31$, $G/d = 4.5$, $D/d = 24.8$.

929 the intermediate range of Γ'_D is of practical importance as real systems, such as aquatic
930 vegetation, offshore structures and foundation piles, typically span this range. Finally, the
931 relation of \overline{C}_d with Γ_D is presented, and it improves our predictive capacity for the bulk
932 bleeding velocity when combined with the universal relation of \bar{u}_p with Γ'_D .

933 **Acknowledgements.** F.H. would like to acknowledge the support from the Australian Government and the
934 University of Western Australia by providing RTP and UPA scholarships for a doctoral degree. This work
935 was supported by resources provided by the Pawsey Supercomputing Centre with funding from the Australian
936 Government and the Government of Western Australia.

937 **Funding.** This research received no specific grant from any funding agency, commercial or not-for-profit
938 sectors.

939 **Declaration of interests.** The authors report no conflict of interest.

940 Author ORCIDs.

- 941 Fei He <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7364-5641>;
942 Hongwei An <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9082-1405>;
943 Marco Ghisalberti <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6690-8922>;
944 Scott Draper <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4185-0111>;
945 Chengjiao Ren <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8342-6522>;
946 Paul Branson <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3825-9873>;
947 Liang Cheng <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1640-542X>.

Q2

948 Appendix A. Numerical validations

949 A.1. Numerical validation for the case of an isolated cylinder

950 The numerical scheme was validated by comparing the results of flow past an isolated
951 cylinder in both 3-D and 3-D simulations with those of existing studies (Norberg 2002;
952 Qu *et al.* 2013; Jiang & Cheng 2021). Figure 22 compares the distribution of pressure
953 coefficient C_p around the cylinder surface, where C_p is defined as $C_p = 2(p - p_\infty)/U_\infty$
954 in which p is the time-averaged kinematic pressure around the cylinder surface and p_∞ is
955 the reference kinematic pressure at the inlet boundary. Flow past an isolated cylinder was
956 modelled at two Reynolds numbers, 200 and 1500. Whilst 200 is equal to the cylinder
957 Reynolds number Re_d defined based on cylinder diameter, 1500 is equal to the array
958 Reynolds number Re_D defined by array diameter when the array approaches a solid body.
959 The pressure coefficient distributions from the present 3-D and 2-D simulations are in
960 excellent agreement with existing studies.

961 A.2. Mesh dependence for an array of 31 cylinders

962 The mesh dependence was checked by quantifying the influence of mesh resolution on
963 the statistical parameters, i.e. the mean drag coefficient of the entire array (\overline{C}_d) and
964 of the centre cylinder ($\overline{C}_{d,16}$ and $\overline{C}_{lrms,16}$) at $(x/D, y/D) = (0, 0)$ in table 2. The results
965 calculated using meshes 2–4 (with varying N_p from 3 to 7 or halving time step Δt) are
966 in excellent agreement with the corresponding values obtained using the reference mesh
967 1. This suggests that the reference mesh is adequate for the numerical simulations of the
968 present study.

969 Appendix B

970 Tables 3 and 4 summarise the testing cases.

F. He and others

Array	N	G/d	D/d	Γ_D	3-D simulations						
					θ	Array	N	G/d	D/d	Γ_D	θ
1*	31	14.7	79	0.50	0°	11*	31	2.7	15.3	2.98	10°
2*	31	14.7	79	0.50	30°	12*	31	2.7	15.3	2.98	30°
3*	31	8	43.3	0.93	0°	13*	31	2.3	13	3.72	30°
4*	31	6	32.7	1.24	0°	14*	31	1.9	11	4.83	30°
5*	31	6	32.7	1.24	30°	15*	31	1.2	7.3	12.61	0°
6*	31	4.5	24.8	1.68	0°	16*	31	1.2	7.3	12.61	30°
7*	31	4.5	24.8	1.68	10°	17*	109	8	85.7	1.65	0°
8*	31	4.5	24.8	1.68	30°	18*	109	4.5	48.6	2.99	0°
9*	31	3.8	21.1	2.01	0°	19*	109	4.5	48.6	2.99	30°
10*	31	2.7	15.3	2.98	0°	20*	109	2.5	27.5	5.91	0°
2-D simulations											
1	7	17.0	35.0	0.26	0°–30°	40	31	2.5	14.2	3.29	0°–30°
2	7	11.0	23.0	0.39	0°–30°	41	31	2.3	13	3.04	30°
3	7	7.5	16	0.57	0°, 30°	42	31	2.08	12.0	4.19	0°–30°
4	7	4.5	10.0	0.96	0°–30°	43	31	1.89	11.0	4.83	0°–30°
5	7	3.6	8.2	1.21	0°	44	31	1.64	9.7	6.07	0°–30°
6	7	3	7	1.49	0°–30°	45	31	1.51	9.0	7.11	0°–30°
7	7	2.7	6.4	1.68	0°	46	31	1.5	8.9	7.29	0°–30°
8	7	2.5	6.0	1.84	0°–30°	47	31	1.4	8.4	8.39	0°–30°
9	7	2	5	2.48	0°	48	31	1.2	7.3	12.93	30°
10	7	1.7	4.4	3.17	0°	49	55	15	109.2	0.64	0°, 30°
11	19	15	61	0.40	0°	50	55	11	80.3	0.88	0°, 30°
12	19	11	45	0.54	0°	51	55	8	58.7	1.21	0°, 30°
13	19	8	33	0.75	0°	52	55	6.5	47.9	1.50	0°
14	19	7	29	0.85	0°	53	55	6	44.3	1.63	0°, 30°
15	19	5.3	22.2	1.13	0°, 30°	54	55	4.5	33.4	2.21	0°
16	19	4.5	19	1.34	0°	55	55	4	29.8	2.51	0°, 30°
17	19	4	17	1.52	0°	56	55	3.6	26.9	2.82	0°
18	19	3.4	14.6	1.82	0°	57	55	3	22.6	3.47	0°, 30°
19	19	3	13	2.10	0°	58	55	2.5	19.0	4.35	0°, 30°
20	19	2.7	11.8	2.38	0°	59	55	2.0	15.4	5.92	0°, 30°
21	19	2.5	11	2.61	0°	60	55	1.6	12.5	8.60	30°
22	31	14.7	79.0	0.50	0°–30°	61	109	17	180.9	0.77	0°–30°
23	31	13	69.8	0.57	0°–30°	62	109	11	117.4	1.19	0°, 30°
24	31	11	59.2	0.67	0°–30°	63	109	9	96	1.46	0°–30°
25	31	9.3	50.0	0.80	0°–30°	64	109	8.0	85.7	1.64	0°–30°
26	31	8	43.3	0.93	0°–30°	65	109	7.5	80.4	1.76	0°, 30°
27	31	7.5	40.7	0.99	0°, 30°	66	109	7	75.1	1.89	0°–30°
28	31	7	38.0	1.06	0°, 30°	67	109	5	53.9	2.68	0°, 30°
29	31	6.0	32.7	1.24	0°–30°	68	109	4.5	48.6	3.00	0°–30°
30	31	5.29	29.0	1.41	0°–30°	69	109	3.6	39.1	3.82	0°, 30°
31	31	4.5	24.8	1.68	0°–30°	70	109	3.2	34.9	4.37	30°
32	31	4.35	24.0	1.74	0°, 30°	71	109	3	32.7	4.73	0°
33	31	4.16	23.0	1.82	0°–30°	72	109	2.7	29.6	5.36	0°, 30°
34	31	4	22.2	1.90	0°–30°	73	109	2.5	27.5	5.90	0°, 30°
35	31	3.8	21.1	2.01	0°, 30°	74	109	2.3	25.3	6.61	0°
36	31	3.4	19.0	2.27	0°–30°	75	109	2	22.2	8.05	0°
37	31	3	16.9	2.62	0°–30°	76	109	1.5	16.9	13.33	0°–30°
38	31	2.7	15.3	2.98	0°–30°	77	109	1.2	13.7	24.2	0°–30°
39	31	2.65	15.0	3.05	0°–30°						

Table 3. Summary of all testing cases. The cases with and without asterisk represent 3-D and 2-D numerical simulations, respectively. Cases simulated with $\theta = 0^\circ, 5^\circ, 10^\circ, 15^\circ, 20^\circ, 25^\circ$ and 30° are denoted "0°–30°".

Case	N	G/d	D/d	Γ_D	Γ'_D ($\theta=0^\circ$)	5°	10°	15°	20°	25°	30°	\bar{u}_p/U_∞ ($\theta=0^\circ$)	5°	10°	15°	20°	25°	30°	
3-D	1*, 2*	31	14.7	79	0.5	0.383	—	—	—	—	—	0.836	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.818
	3*	31	8	43.3	0.9	0.683	—	—	—	—	—	0.7228	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	4*, 5*	31	6	32.7	1.2	0.819	—	—	—	—	—	1.077	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.5645
	6*, 8*	31	4.5	24.8	1.7	0.939	—	—	—	—	—	1.293	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.4596
	9*	31	3.8	21.1	2.0	1.110	—	—	—	—	—	1.338	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.2268
	10*, 12*	31	2.7	15.3	3.0	1.137	—	—	—	—	—	1.500	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.196
	13*	31	2.3	13	3.7	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.933	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.1694
	14*	31	1.9	11	4.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	3.740	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.056
	15*, 16*	31	1.2	7.3	12.6	3.736	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	17*	109	8	85.7	1.6	1.031	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
2-D	18*, 19*	109	4.5	48.6	3	1.265	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	20*	109	2.5	27.5	5.9	1.541	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	1	7	17.0	35.0	0.3	0.230	0.282	0.333	0.332	0.334	0.333	0.279	0.878	0.875	0.878	0.875	0.874	0.874	0.875
	2	7	11.0	23.0	0.4	0.338	—	—	—	—	—	0.424	0.833	—	—	—	—	—	0.814
	8	7	2.5	6.0	1.8	1.184	—	—	—	—	—	1.535	0.475	—	—	—	—	—	0.301
	22	31	14.7	79.0	0.5	0.391	0.490	0.581	0.569	0.546	0.560	0.467	0.834	0.817	0.789	0.796	0.812	0.800	0.829
	28	31	7	38.0	1.1	0.745	—	—	—	—	—	0.935	0.696	—	—	—	—	—	0.632
	29	31	6.0	32.7	1.2	0.821	—	—	—	—	—	1.104	0.660	—	—	—	—	—	0.566
	31	31	5.3	29.0	1.4	0.861	0.896	1.026	1.137	1.159	1.182	1.166	0.635	0.611	0.564	0.559	0.534	0.527	0.518
	33	31	4.2	23.0	1.8	0.995	1.074	1.096	1.215	1.276	1.317	1.317	0.578	0.528	0.499	0.495	0.461	0.430	0.432
36	31	3.4	19.0	2.3	1.286	—	—	—	—	—	1.383	0.451	—	—	—	—	—	0.356	
38	31	2.7	15.3	3.0	1.151	—	—	—	—	—	1.410	0.340	—	—	—	—	—	0.238	
39	31	2.6	15.0	3.1	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.417	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.228	
42	31	2.1	12.0	4.2	1.573	1.546	1.544	1.578	1.685	1.757	1.986	0.239	0.250	0.236	0.202	0.202	0.201	0.210	
43	31	1.9	11.0	4.8	1.776	1.781	1.822	1.840	1.922	—	2.25	0.196	0.206	0.193	0.176	0.181	0.199	0.199	
44	31	1.6	9.7	6.1	2.798	2.700	2.681	2.709	2.814	2.780	2.745	0.174	0.182	0.171	0.168	0.178	0.173	0.165	
45	31	1.5	9.0	7.1	3.362	3.366	3.180	3.138	3.282	3.240	3.210	0.154	0.161	0.151	0.149	0.167	0.155	0.144	
48	31	1.2	7.3	12.6	—	—	—	—	—	—	3.809	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.10611	
50	55	11	80.3	0.9	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.803	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.722	
59	55	2.0	15.4	5.9	1.693	—	—	—	—	—	2.322	0.163	—	—	—	—	—	0.178	
61	109	17	180.9	0.8	0.616	0.678	0.763	0.757	0.758	0.711	0.718	0.801	0.814	0.769	0.764	0.757	0.785	0.764	
68	109	4.5	48.6	3.0	1.312	1.317	1.301	1.317	1.363	1.410	1.463	0.409	0.414	0.435	0.418	0.370	0.334	0.332	
72	109	2.7	29.5	5.4	1.587	—	—	—	—	—	1.716	0.224	—	—	—	—	—	0.208	
76	109	1.5	16.9	13.3	3.540	—	—	—	—	—	3.506	0.176	—	—	—	—	—	0.126	
77	109	1.2	13.7	24.2	5.580	—	—	—	—	—	5.063	0.117	—	—	—	—	—	0.089	

Table 4. Summary of testing cases from 3-D and 2-D simulations shown in figure 19. The case numbers correspond to those of table 3. The two cases marked in bold text are cited in § 3.4, with flow fields shown in figure 23. The columns of Γ'_D and \bar{u}_p/U_∞ are denoted with **text** only for $\theta=0^\circ$.

- 972 BALL, D., STANSBY, P., ALLISON, N. & STROUHAL 1996 Modelling shallow water flow around pile groups.
973 *Proc. Inst. Civil Engrs Water Maritime Energy* **118**, 226–236.
- 974 BAO, Y., ZHOU, D. & HUANG, C. 2010 Numerical simulation of flow over three circular cylinders in
975 equilateral arrangements at low Reynolds number by a second-order characteristic-based split finite element
976 method. *Comput. Fluids* **39**, 882–899.
- 977 BLACKBURN, H.M. & SHERWIN, S.J. 2004 Formulation of a Galerkin spectral element–Fourier method for
978 three-dimensional incompressible flows in cylindrical geometries. *J. Comput. Phys.* **197**, 759–778.
- 979 CANTWELL, C.D., MOXEY, D., COMERFORD, A., BOLIS, A., ROCCO, G., *et al.* 2015 Nektar++: an
980 open-source spectral/hp element framework. *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **192**, 205–219.
- 981 CHANG, K. & CONSTANTINESCU, G. 2015 Numerical investigation of flow and turbulence structure through
982 and around a circular array of rigid cylinders. *J. Fluid Mech.* **776**, 161–199.
- 983 CHANG, W.-Y., CONSTANTINESCU, G. & TSAI, W.F. 2017 On the flow and coherent structures generated by
984 a circular array of rigid emerged cylinders placed in an open channel with flat and deformed bed. *J. Fluid*
985 *Mech.* **831**, 1–40.
- 986 CHEN, W., JI, C., ALAM, M.M., WILLIAMS, J. & XU, D. 2020 Numerical simulations of flow past three
987 circular cylinders in equilateral-triangular arrangements. *J. Fluid Mech.* **891**.
- Q7 988 CHEN, Z., ORTIZ, A., ZONG, L. & NEPF, H. 2012 The wake structure behind a porous obstruction and its
989 implications for deposition near a finite patch of emergent vegetation. *Water Resour. Res.* **48**.
- Q8 990 CHENG, N.-S., HUI, C.L., WANG, X. & TAN, S.K. 2019 Laboratory study of porosity effect on drag induced
991 by circular vegetative patch. *J. Engng Mech.* **145**, 04019046.
- Q9 992 DRAPER, S. & NISHINO, T. 2014 Centred and staggered arrangements of tidal turbines. *J. Fluid Mech.* **739**,
993 72–93.
- 994 DURGIN, W.W. & KARLSSON, S.K.F. 1971 On the phenomenon of vortex street breakdown. *J. Fluid Mech.*
995 **48**, 507–527.
- 996 EIZADI, H., AN, H., ZHOU, T., ZHU, H. & CHENG, L. 2022 Wake transitions of six tandem circular cylinders
997 at low Reynolds numbers. *Phys. Fluids* **34**, 023605.
- 998 FIABANE, L., GOHLKE, M. & CADOT, O. 2011 Characterization of flow contributions to drag and lift of a
999 circular cylinder using a volume expression of the fluid force. *Eur. J. Mech. (B/Fluids)* **30**, 311–315.
- 1000 FONSECA, M.S., KOEHL, M. & KOPP, B.S. 2007 Biomechanical factors contributing to self-organization in
1001 seagrass landscapes. *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.* **340**, 227–246.
- 1002 GAO, Y., CHEN, W., WANG, B. & WANG, L. 2020 Numerical simulation of the flow past six-circular
1003 cylinders in rectangular configurations. *J. Mar. Sci. Technol.* **25**, 718–742.
- 1004 GUERMOND, J.-L. & SHEN, J. 2003 Velocity-correction projection methods for incompressible flows. *SIAM*
1005 *J. Numer. Anal.* **41**, 112–134.
- 1006 HE, F. 2023 Hydrodynamics within and behind a porous obstruction in steady flow. Doctoral thesis, The
1007 University of Western Australia, Perth.
- 1008 HE, F., DRAPER, S., GHISALBERTI, M., AN, H., BRANSON, P., *et al.* 2022 Wake structure behind porous
1009 obstructions in steady current. In *23rd Australasian Fluid Mechanics Conference*, Sydney, Australia.
- Q10 1010 HE, F., GHISALBERTI, M., AN, H., DRAPER, S., BRANSON, P., *et al.* 2024 Wake structure of an array of
1011 cylinders in shallow flow. *J. Fluid Mech.* **986**, A30.
- Q11 1012 HOSSEINI, N., GRIFFITH, M. & LEONTINI, J. 2020 The flow past large numbers of cylinders in tandem.
1013 *J. Fluids Struct.* **98**, 103103.
- 1014 JIANG, H. & CHENG, L. 2021 Large-eddy simulation of flow past a circular cylinder for Reynolds numbers
1015 400 to 3900. *Phys. Fluids* **33**, 034119.
- 1016 JIANG, H., CHENG, L., DRAPER, S. & AN, H. 2017 Three-dimensional wake transition for a circular cylinder
1017 near a moving wall. *J. Fluid Mech.* **818**, 260–287.
- 1018 JIANG, H., CHENG, L., DRAPER, S., AN, H. & TONG, F. 2016 Three-dimensional direct numerical
1019 simulation of wake transitions of a circular cylinder. *J. Fluid Mech.* **801**, 353–391.
- 1020 KARASUDANI, T. & FUNAKOSHI, M. 1994 Evolution of a vortex street in the far wake of a cylinder. *Fluid*
1021 *Dyn. Res.* **14**, 331.
- 1022 KARNIADAKIS, G.E., ISRAELI, M. & ORSZAG, S.A. 1991 High-order splitting methods for the
1023 incompressible Navier–Stokes equations. *J. Comput. Phys.* **97**, 414–443.
- 1024 KOCH, E.W., ACKERMAN, J.D., VERDUIN, J. & VAN KEULEN, M. 2007 Fluid dynamics in seagrass
1025 ecology—from molecules to ecosystems In *Seagrasses: Biology, Ecology and Conservation*, pp. 193–225.
1026 Springer.
- 1027 KODA, Y. & LIEN, F.-S. 2013 Aerodynamic effects of the early three-dimensional instabilities in the flow over
1028 one and two circular cylinders in tandem predicted by the lattice Boltzmann method. *Comput. Fluids* **74**,
1029 32–43.

Obstacle arrangement can control flows

- 1030 LAM, K., LI, J. & SO, R. 2003 Force coefficients and Strouhal numbers of four cylinders in cross flow.
1031 *J. Fluids Struct.* **18**, 305–324.
- 1032 NAIR, A., KAZEMI, A., CURET, O. & VERMA, S. 2023 Porous cylinder arrays for optimal wake and drag
1033 characteristics. *J. Fluid Mech.* **961**, A18.
- 1034 NICOLLE, A. & EAMES, I. 2011 Numerical study of flow through and around a circular array of cylinders.
1035 *J. Fluid Mech.* **679**, 1–31.
- 1036 NORBERG, C. 2002 *Symposium on Bluff Body Wakes and Vortex-Induced Vibrations (BBVIV3)*, 17–20. Port
1037 Arthur, Queensland, Australia. Monash University, Melbourne.
- 1038 QU, L., NORBERG, C., DAVIDSON, L., PENG, S.-H. & WANG, F. 2013 Quantitative numerical analysis of
1039 flow past a circular cylinder at Reynolds number between 50 and 200. *J. Fluids Struct.* **39**, 347–370.
- 1040 REN, C., CHENG, L., TONG, F., XIONG, C. & CHEN, T. 2019 Oscillatory flow regimes around four cylinders
1041 in a diamond arrangement. *J. Fluid Mech.* **877**, 955–1006.
- 1042 REN, C., CHENG, L., XIONG, C., TONG, F. & CHEN, T. 2021a Bistabilities in two parallel Kármán wakes.
1043 *J. Fluid Mech.* **929**. Q12
- 1044 REN, C., LIU, Z., CHENG, L., TONG, F. & XIONG, C. 2023 Three-dimensional wake transitions of steady
1045 flow past two side-by-side cylinders. *J. Fluid Mech.* **972**, A17.
- 1046 REN, C., LU, L., CHENG, L. & CHEN, T. 2021b Hydrodynamic damping of an oscillating cylinder at small
1047 Keulegan–Carpenter numbers. *J. Fluid Mech.* **913**. Q13
- 1048 ROMINGER, J.T. & NEPF, H.M. 2011 Flow adjustment and interior flow associated with a rectangular porous
1049 obstruction. *J. Fluid Mech.* **680**, 636–659.
- 1050 SAHIN, M. & OWENS, R.G. 2004 A numerical investigation of wall effects up to high blockage ratios on
1051 two-dimensional flow past a confined circular cylinder. *Phys. Fluids* **16**, 1305–1320.
- 1052 DA SILVA, B.L., LUCIANO, R.D., UTZIG, J. & MEIER, H.F. 2019 Analysis of flow behavior and fluid forces
1053 in large cylinder bundles by numerical simulations. *Intl J. Heat Fluid Flow* **75**, 209–226.
- 1054 SUMNER, D. 2010 Two circular cylinders in cross-flow: a review. *J. Fluids Struct.* **26**, 849–899.
- 1055 TAKEMURA, T. & TANAKA, N. 2007 Flow structures and drag characteristics of a colony-type emergent
1056 roughness model mounted on a flat plate in uniform flow. *Fluid Dyn. Res.* **39**, 694.
- 1057 TANINO, Y. & NEPF, H.M. 2008 Laboratory investigation of mean drag in a random array of rigid, emergent
1058 cylinders. *J. Hydraul. Engng ASCE* **134**, 34–41.
- 1059 THOMPSON, M.C., RADI, A., RAO, A., SHERIDAN, J. & HOURIGAN, K. 2014 Low-Reynolds-number wakes
1060 of elliptical cylinders: from the circular cylinder to the normal flat plate. *J. Fluid Mech.* **751**, 570–600.
- 1061 TONG, F., CHENG, L., ZHAO, M., ZHOU, T. & CHEN, X.-B. 2014 The vortex shedding around four circular
1062 cylinders in an in-line square configuration. *Phys. Fluids* **26**, 024112.
- 1063 VOS, P.E., ESKILSSON, C., BOLIS, A., CHUN, S., KIRBY, R.M. & SHERWIN, S.J. 2011 A generic
1064 framework for time-stepping partial differential equations (PDEs): general linear methods, object-oriented
1065 implementation and application to fluid problems. *Intl J. Comput. Fluid Dyn.* **25**, 107–125.
- 1066 WANG, X., GONG, K., LIU, H., ZHANG, J.-X. & TAN, S. 2013 Flow around four cylinders arranged in a
1067 square configuration. *J. Fluids Struct.* **43**, 179–199.
- 1068 WILLIAMSON, C.H.K. 1996 Three-dimensional wake transition. *J. Fluid Mech.* **328**, 345–407.
- 1069 YIN, J.-J., JIA, T., GAO, D. & XIAO, F. 2020 Numerical investigation of the patterns of the flow past nine
1070 cylinders at low Reynolds number. *AIP Adv.* **10**, 085107.
- 1071 ZDRAVKOVICH, M. 1977 Review of flow interference between two circular cylinders in various arrangements. Q14
1072 ZDRAVKOVICH, M.M. 1997 *Flow around Circular Cylinders: Volume 2: Applications*. Oxford University
1073 Press.
- 1074 ZHAO, M., CHENG, L., AN, H. & TONG, F. 2015 Flow and flow-induced vibration of a square array of
1075 cylinders in steady currents. *Fluid Dyn. Res.* **47**, 045505.
- 1076 ZHOU, Y. & ALAM, M.M. 2016 Wake of two interacting circular cylinders: a review. *Intl J. Heat Fluid Flow*
1077 **62**, 510–537.
- 1078 ZHU, H., ZHONG, J. & ZHOU, T. 2021 Wake structure characteristics of three tandem circular cylinders at a
1079 low Reynolds number of 160. *Phys. Fluids* **33**, 044113.
- 1080 ZIADA, S. 2006 Vorticity shedding and acoustic resonance in tube bundles. *J. Braz. Soc. Mech. Sci. Engng* **28**,
1081 186–189.
- 1082 ZONG, L. & NEPF, H. 2012 Vortex development behind a finite porous obstruction in a channel. *J. Fluid Mech.*
1083 **691**, 368–391.